

**METACOGNITIVE AWARENESS AND WORK TASK MOTIVATION
AS PREDICTORS OF TEACHING COMPETENCE AMONG
PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS:
A CONVERGENT DESIGN**

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Metacognitive Awareness and Work Task Motivation as Predictors of Teaching Competence among Public Elementary School Teachers: A Convergent Design

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Abstract

Teaching competence is a set of personal characteristics or habits that results in more effective and superior job performance. Thus in this study, the researcher tried to determine the influence of metacognitive awareness and work task motivation on the teaching competence of public elementary school teachers in Region XI, conceptualized through the pragmatic philosophical worldview. Mixed methods research approach specifically the convergent design was employed in this study. Public elementary school teachers in the Davao Region served as respondents, purposively chosen both for the quantitative phase and in the focus group discussion and in-depth interview for the qualitative phase. Adapted questionnaires and interview guides were utilized for the gathering of data. Statistical tools like mean, standard deviation, and multiple regression analysis were used to analyze the quantitative data while thematic analysis was applied in the qualitative phase. Findings revealed that the status of metacognitive awareness, work task motivation, and teaching competence were rated very high among public elementary school teachers. Further, in an individual capacity, the metacognitive awareness of public elementary school teachers was not a significant predictor of the teaching competence of public elementary school teachers. Furthermore, results indicated that work task motivation was a significant predictor of the teaching competence of public elementary school teachers. However, the combined effect of metacognitive awareness and work task motivation as predictors of teaching competence was a good fit for the data in this study. Moreover, essential themes emerged from the thematic analysis of the participants' lived experiences such as; appropriateness of learning-task designs, mindfulness of teaching-learning strategies, established teacher presence, higher-level thinking skills reinforcement, and discipline and morale maintenance. More so, the participants' experiences played a significant role in shaping their beliefs, which resulted in the theme of teaching with a heart, for their attitudes, the theme that emerged was thoughtfulness in pedagogy, and for their commitment, it was steadfast in teaching. Interestingly, mixing the salient quantitative and qualitative findings revealed the merging-converging nature and function of data integration.

Keywords: *education, leadership, metacognitive awareness, work task motivation, teaching competence*

Introduction

The widely accepted concept of teaching competence, which emanated from the ideas of Hargreaves and Fullan (2012), views teaching competence as an evolving and dynamic concept. It emphasizes the need for teachers to continuously refine their skills, adapt to changing educational contexts, and stay updated with advancements in the field. This construct encompasses not only the initial knowledge and skills that teachers possess but also the ongoing process of professional development throughout their careers. As education continues to evolve, it underlines how certain teaching competence can be acquired and efficiently delivered to students. However, one issue that is faced in the academe is inexperienced and incompetent teachers. Incompetent teachers are estimated to comprise about 5-10 percent of the teaching force in an institution (Yariv, 2004).

Moreover, as emphasized by Sumantri and Whardani (2017), one of the major issues contributing to low educational quality and the need for teacher motivation is the low competence of teachers who work in a variety of basic educational contexts. Many teachers' poor competencies demonstrate this issue. Teachers lack competence in facilitating the learning process; some cannot design and foster learning and interpersonal skills, and much more, they are not supported by adequate facilities. More so, teachers must also increase their competence to teach and master the subjects they teach.

The study conducted by Sandriyani et al. (2021) in Palembang, South of Sumatera, Indonesia, revealed that based on the findings of preliminary observations, the researchers discovered indicators that there are some concerns with teachers' competence. There are still teachers who are not competent with the teaching material, who use learning strategies that are not in line with the applicable curriculum, who lack administrative preparation for the learning process, who are not competent with technology-based tools, who do not employ a variety of learning models, and who otherwise cause the learning process to become monotonous.

Additionally, less than 40 percent of teachers in Indonesia held bachelor's degrees, which are considered to be low-level qualifications. In addition, many teachers lacked the fundamental subject knowledge and pedagogical abilities necessary to be successful educators. A competency test for teachers was introduced by the central government in 2012 to evaluate their subject knowledge and pedagogical abilities. In 2015, nearly three million teachers who took the test fell short of the specified target of 55 (Rosser, 2018). Additionally, the majority of the teachers at five schools in India were assessed as ineffective and in need of improvement. Over 50 percent of their teachers were incompetent (Mcinerny, 2016).

Furthermore, in Edo State, Nigeria, researchers discovered that little is known about the teacher's role as a model in metacognitive

strategies; that is, setting the example for learners and providing feedback. When questioned about the use of the concept of metacognition in the classroom, the interviewees' responses revealed that they were inexperienced with its significance. A deeper look at how metacognition is used in their teachings revealed a dearth of knowledge (Okoza & Aluede, 2013). Further, Okoza and Imhonde (2010) discovered in their study that teachers and students frequently failed to reflect on and regulate their teaching and learning strategically.

In the Philippine setting, Ambag (2014) stated that having competent teachers who are of high caliber is essential. Garcines (2018) noted that, after vetting teacher applications for a teaching position, some had not operated as competently as expected after being hired. This occurrence has concerned him because it may have an impact on the learners' growth. According to Basadre (2001), students truly desire to have competent teachers and demonstrate mastery of the course they are teaching. This is because their competency is defined as the sum of their abilities. Furthermore, their competence is their most effective tool.

In CARAGA Region XIII, District of Talacogon, Agusan del Sur, Avila and Baetiong, (2012) revealed that teachers lacked the same level of competency when it came to activities like boosting students' sense of interest, asking questions that required higher-order mental capacities, learning and evaluating novel ideas and concepts, and responding to circumstances though they were found to be effective in preparing courses that were suited to the learners' aptitude and capacity, as well as igniting students' preexisting ideas or preconceived notions about the subjects being covered. More so, the results show that for teachers to improve and reach effectiveness in their teaching competence, the tasks where they performed so poorly must be given more focus.

Upon conducting a comprehensive review of the related literature, the researcher identified metacognitive awareness as a potential factor influencing teaching competence. Several studies have explored the relationship between metacognitive awareness and teaching competence. Adding on, Balcikanli (2011) emphasized the significance of metacognitive awareness as an accelerating element in the teaching-learning process. By being aware of their own cognitive processes and having a deeper understanding of their instructional practices, teachers can make purposeful adjustments and improvements to enhance student learning outcomes.

Additionally, metacognitive approaches to teaching and learning emphasize the importance of teachers being aware of their own thinking processes and strategically using metacognitive strategies in their instructional practices. When teachers possess a strong metacognitive awareness, they are better equipped to reflect on their teaching methods, monitor their instructional effectiveness, and make informed decisions to optimize student learning outcomes (Perry et al., 2019). Thus, the findings suggest that by harnessing the power of metacognition, teachers can enhance their teaching competence and significantly improve the educational outcomes of children. Thus, cultivating teachers' metacognitive awareness can serve as a valuable pathway for promoting effective teaching practices and facilitating meaningful learning experiences.

As underscored by Hattie (2003) a teacher must be competent in specific metacognitive skills to recognize and assess his or her work to be upgraded with the current educational system. To foster metacognition in schools, teachers must be well-versed in metacognitive teaching techniques. Thus, teachers must educate competently to deliver quality education to all learners, to be competent individuals of this age who can apply knowledge to real-life problems.

Also, the findings of the published studies single out work task motivation as a potential antecedent for predicting teaching competence. On the one hand, teachers' work task motivation is a significant component in affecting teacher competence (Kompri, 2016). Moreover, if there is a driving drive, such as motivation, the teacher will display an interest in carrying out a task or event and then perform it successfully (Darmiati et al., 2020). On the other hand, Kunter et al. (2013) examined the relationship between teacher competence, instructional quality, and student development. They found that teachers with higher levels of work task motivation demonstrated greater instructional quality, utilizing effective teaching practices such as clear explanations and engaging methods. This instructional quality positively impacted student development, leading to improved academic achievement and socio-emotional outcomes. These findings emphasize the significance of work task motivation in enhancing teacher competence and the quality of instruction, ultimately benefiting student learning and well-being.

More importantly, the results of this study will play a crucial role in the development of effective and innovative professional leadership programs for DepEd school teachers. These programs will be rooted in thorough research, aiming to enhance teachers' motivation in their work tasks and foster metacognitive awareness, thereby empowering the teaching-learning process. Moreover, the study's findings will serve as a valuable resource for future research endeavors in the field of educational leadership. variables such as the quality of relationships, school composition, teacher characteristics, career aspirations, and organizational and work commitment. It is worth noting that these studies were predominantly conducted in different countries. For instance, Khatoon et al. (2011) conducted a study aiming to identify sociocultural problems and environmental issues faced by female school teachers, while also assessing teaching competence by examining the interaction between teachers and students. However, there remains a dearth of research investigating other variables crucial to teaching competence. Notably, studies by Marzano et al. (2003) have emphasized the significance of effective classroom management and pedagogical content knowledge in enhancing teaching competence, while research conducted by Roorda et al. (2011) has underscored the impact of positive teacher-student relationships and reflective practice on teaching effectiveness. Consequently, this knowledge gap necessitates further research.

With all these compelling reasons, the researcher aims to address this gap by conducting a study using a mixed methods approach,

particularly a convergent design, to explore and understand the link between metacognitive awareness of teaching, work task motivation, and teaching competence in public elementary schools in Region XI, Philippines.

Furthermore, despite the existence of numerous publications and research studies on teaching competence worldwide, a research gap becomes apparent when examining the lack of local studies employing mixed methods to investigate the relationship between metacognitive awareness, motivation, and teaching competence. Additionally, there is a scarcity of studies that have employed descriptive approaches for data collection and analysis in the specific context of public elementary school teachers. Moreover, within the bounds of Region XI, no mixed methods designs have been found in reports and books concerning teaching competence predicted by metacognitive awareness and work task motivation.

Importantly, to ensure widespread dissemination of the study, the results will be shared through school learning action cells (LAC) sessions, seminars, and training programs organized by the DepEd- Region XI schools division offices, as well as through local, national, and international research conferences. This comprehensive approach guarantees that the study's impact will reach a broad audience, benefiting educational practitioners and researchers alike. The researcher will also take into consideration an online publication of this study for easy access and extensive dissemination of the research work.

Research Questions

This study determined the influence of metacognitive awareness and work task motivation on the teaching competence of public elementary school teachers using the convergent mixed methods in the selected public elementary schools in Region XI. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the status of metacognitive awareness, work task motivation, and teaching competence?
2. Do metacognitive awareness and work task motivation significantly predict teaching competence?
3. What are the lived experiences of public elementary school teachers as regards their teaching competence?
4. How do these experiences shape the beliefs, attitudes, and commitments of public elementary school teachers pertaining to their teaching competence?
5. To what extent do the qualitative data corroborate with the quantitative findings?

Methodology

Research Design

This research employed the mixed methods approach specifically the convergent design. A mixed methods study combines qualitative and quantitative methodologies for the research purpose of accomplishing partnership, breadth, and depth of understanding (Johnson et al., 2007). Further, according to Creswell, (2008) the mixed methods design is used for conducting research that involves collecting, analyzing, and integrating quantitative and qualitative research in a single study or a longitudinal program of inquiry. Furthermore, the purpose of this form of research is that both quantitative and qualitative research, in combination, will provide a better understanding of a research problem or issue than either research approach alone. More so, this design was assumed to provide a complete understanding of the metacognitive awareness, work task motivation, and teaching competence among public elementary school teachers.

Specifically, in this study, the researcher employed the convergent design also known as convergent parallel design. A research method known as the convergent parallel can be written as QUAL+QUAN (Morse, 1991). Due to its design, the researcher must simultaneously complete both quantitative and qualitative components at the same stage of the research process, weigh the approaches equally, separately analyze the two components, and jointly interpret the results (Creswell & Clark, 2011). Additionally, by comparing quantitative statistical data with qualitative conclusions, the researcher hopes to triangulate the methodologies. Likewise, the researcher will desire to determine how well qualitative and quantitative data corroborate.

Furthermore, in the quantitative strand, the researcher employed the descriptive-correlational analysis. Descriptive correlation design seeks to describe the variables in the study through appropriate measurements and focused more on examining the degree of association or relation of one or more variables using the statistical procedure of correlational analysis. The correlational study is concerned with the establishment of correlations between more than one variable within the same population or between the same variables in two populations (Leedy & Ormrod, 2010 as cited by Curtis et al., 2015). For this study, the variables which were correlated included the metacognitive awareness, work task motivation, and teaching competence among public elementary school teachers in the Davao Region. Moreover, the researcher adapted survey questionnaires from the previous similar studies using a five- point Likert Scale. Results obtained in this method were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools to come up with appropriate conclusions and generalizations. This method examined if cognitive awareness and work task motivation influence teaching competence.

In addition, in the qualitative phase of the research, phenomenological research design was employed. The researcher used the phenomenological approach that reflects epistemological perspective, believing that the validity of truth is multiple and subjective. A phenomenological study describes the common meaning for several individuals of their lived experiences of a concept or phenomenon. It focuses on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group (Creswell, 2013). Additionally, in this study, the

participants' lived experiences of their metacognitive awareness and work task motivation as predictors of teaching competence were explored and how these experiences shaped the beliefs, attitudes, and commitments of public elementary school teachers in the Davao Region pertaining to their teaching competence. Figure 1 depicts the concept of convergent parallel design.

Figure 1. Convergent Design

Figure 1 presents the convergent design that was utilized in this study. It shows that quantitative data on the metacognitive awareness, work task motivation, and teaching competence were collected and analyzed concurrently using the qualitative data derived from the participants' lived experience regarding the metacognitive awareness of teaching, teachers' work task motivation, and teaching competence of teachers and examined whether it confirmed or contradicted each other.

Participants

Quantitative Strand. The respondents of the study were the 400 public elementary school teachers from the selected public elementary schools in the Davao Region. Purposive sampling was employed in the selection of the respondents and the sample size was based on the Slovin's Formula. Purposive sampling is a technique which involves the selection of study participants based on the criteria set by the researcher, and this ensures homogeneity of the sample population (Creswell, 2017).

To attain homogeneity, certain inclusion criteria was implemented to determine the teacher- respondents. The primary consideration of this study was to choose teacher-respondents who could provide vital information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, participants should be the full-time teachers and had been teaching in the public elementary schools with at least three-year teaching experience in the organization or more, regardless of the subject they were teaching or any grade level they handled, and willing to spend time to engage in the study being chosen. Any respondent who did not meet such criteria was automatically excluded in this study.

Qualitative Strand. In the qualitative phase, the participants were the 17 public elementary school teachers. There were 10 involved in the IDI, and seven for the FGD. The participants were selected through purposive sampling which was similarly done in the selection of respondents in the quantitative strand. The choice of subjects according to Seargent (2012) will be purposeful in qualitative terms; participants according to him will be chosen among those who can better answer research questions and understand the phenomenon under study. As emphasized by Creswell (2017), a homogenous group may vary in size from three to four individuals to 10-15. The participants were chosen according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria followed in the quantitative strand but were separate from the 400 teacher-respondents in quantitative strand. The results of the IDI and FGD were utilized to explore the emerging themes based on their experiences.

Instrument

Quantitative Strand. In the quantitative strand, adapted questionnaires were utilized to gather data from the respondents. The instruments adapted are composed of three survey tools which are as follows: In Metacognitive Awareness, the instrument was adapted from the "Metacognitive Awareness Inventory for Teachers" developed by Balcikanli (2011). The validity of the inventory was 0.794 whereas; the reliability of the tool was found high and ranged from 0.79 to 0.85. The items are distributed into six indicators namely, declarative knowledge, procedural knowledge, conditional knowledge, planning, monitoring, and evaluating. The tool is a 24-item modification consisting of 4 items in each factor with responses on a five-point Likert scale where '1' as the lowest score described as strongly disagree, '2' disagree, '3' moderately agree, '4' agree, and '5' as the highest score describe as strongly agree.

Additionally, the Work Tasks Motivation Scale for Teachers (WTMST) was developed by Fernet et al. (2008). Internal consistency values are evaluated for the five types of motivation among the five work tasks. Cronbach's values ranged from .83 to .96 (mean $r = .92$) for intrinsic motivation, .72 to .89 (mean $r = .82$) for identified regulation, .79 to .89 (mean $r = .85$) for introjected regulation, .64 to .87 (mean $r = .76$) for external regulation, and .75 to .81 (mean $r = .77$) for amotivation. Overall, internal consistency values met the criterion of .70 proposed by Nunnally (1978). The tool is a 15- item construct consisting of three items in each indicator with responses on a five-point Likert scale where '1' as the lowest score describe as strongly disagree, '2' disagree, '3' moderately agree, '4' agree, and '5' as the highest score describe as strongly agree.

Moreover, the "General Teaching Competence Scale" was developed and standardized by (B. K. Passi & S. Lalitha, 1994). The inter-

observer reliability of the scale was reported to be ranging from 0.85 to 0.91, and the factorial validity was measured, which ranged from 0.78 to 0.82. The entire teaching-learning process in the classroom is covered by 21 components that are related to 21 teaching competencies. They are related to five major aspects of classroom teaching, namely, planning, presentation, closing, evaluation, and managerial. The tool is a 21-item construct with responses on a five-point Likert scale where '1' as the lowest score describe as strongly disagree, '2' disagree, '3' moderately agree, '4' agree, and '5' as the highest score describe as strongly agree.

Qualitative Strand. To gather qualitative data, the researcher constructed an interview guide consisting open-ended questions for the IDI and FGD. The interview guide used in this study underwent a process of content validation. According to DeVellis (2016), content validation is a method that ensures the accuracy, relevance, and appropriateness of the items included in the interview guide. During this process, experts or knowledgeable individuals in the field reviewed the interview guide to assess its content validity.

They examined the questions and assessed whether they effectively captured the intended constructs or topics of interest. The experts provided feedback, suggestions, and recommendations to refine and improve the interview guide. This content validation process helps to enhance the quality and validity of the interview guide, ensuring that it effectively measures the intended variables and provides reliable and meaningful data for the research study.

Moreover, the same questions were utilized in both IDI and FGD for comparative purposes and to make sure that the crucial questions were retained for the interview. Thematic analysis was used to categorize and evaluate the participants' lived experiences. Thematic analysis is a data analysis plan that is commonly used by qualitative researchers to generate themes from interview data. In addition, it is a technique for methodically identifying, categorizing, and providing insight into patterns of meaning or themes across data that allows the researcher to comprehend shared or collective meanings and experiences by focusing on meaning across a dataset (Braun & Clarke, 2012).

Procedure

Quantitative Strand. Before the research was conducted, a letter requesting permission to conduct the research was sent to the Graduate School Dean of the University of the Immaculate Conception (UIC). Before data collection, the researcher submitted the manuscript to the office of UIC Research Ethics Committee (UICREC) to guarantee that it was ethically sound. Once the Ethical Clearance was received, the researcher sought permission to conduct the study from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent and the District Supervisor of each province in the Davao Region.

Additionally, the researcher also asked the principals or school leaders of the province's selected DepEd elementary school levels for their approval. Once approved, the researcher handed out the Informed Consent Form (ICF) to the respondents and requested that they will read and sign the form before participating in the study. Their participation was entirely voluntary, as indicated in the ICF, and only those who affirmed their willingness to engage in the study were permitted to complete the survey questionnaire in the quantitative phase as well as in the qualitative phase. Respondents had the option of withdrawing from the study at any moment with no penalty or loss of reward. Respondents were informed that their responses and identities will be kept strictly confidential.

Qualitative Strand. In obtaining qualitative data about how the participants think and feel in the most direct ways, the researcher conducted in-depth one-on-one interviewing, direct participant observations, and focus group discussion. According to Creswell (2007), qualitative researchers would be involved in several tasks during the data collection phase. Thus, an important factor that the researcher considered is the feasibility of the materials required, the research participants who were included in the study, and the setting in which the researcher conducted the study to gather and obtain essential information to answer the purpose of this study. The researcher obtained an endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School of UIC indicating that the researcher had permission to perform the study. The researcher then sought approval from the relevant individuals to conduct this study and administer an interview with the selected participants.

In addition, the purposive sampling method was used to identify the participants. The researcher secured the key participants and used open-ended queries to gather vital information for the study. In the event that the participants expressed an interest in participating in the IDI and FGD, the researcher then informed them about the study and discussed the completion of informed consent forms with them. They were also requested to sign the consent form after they have consented to participate on their own to demonstrate their voluntary participation and that they are fully aware of the scope of the study. The researcher explained the study's aim, the protocol's structure, and the participants' rights and privileges such as the right to withdraw from the study and confidentiality.

Further, to help collect all the data from the participants, the researcher employed an audio recorder. According to Audu (2016) as cited by Garing (2021), the purpose of the audio-taped recording is to make sure that the participant data will be saved and stored, and then after the interview, the responses will be transcribed. For added security in case of malfunction, the researcher also recorded interviews on a laptop, which will be extremely useful for transcribing the data. To capture the research participants' non-verbal answers, the researcher also took down notes. Furthermore, to ensure that the data are precise and accurate, the researcher transcribed participant responses verbatim or word-for-word. Moreover, the thematic analysis was then carried out. The researcher, with aid of the adviser, ensured that the central concepts were evaluated in light of the participant's responses.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Strand. The analysis of quantitative data was conducted through the use of appropriate statistical tools such as mean, standard deviation, and multiple regression analysis.

Mean. For this study, the mean was used to determine the levels of metacognitive awareness of teaching, teachers' work task motivation, and teaching competence among public elementary teachers in the Davao Region. Standard deviation was utilized to measure the amount of dispersion of a set of data values on the status of metacognitive awareness on teaching, teachers' work task motivation, and teaching competence among public elementary teachers in Davao Region.

Additionally, the multiple regression analysis was employed to determine the influence of the attributes of metacognitive awareness on teaching, teachers' work task motivation, and teaching competence among public elementary teachers in the Davao Region.

Qualitative Strand. As part of the qualitative phase, several approaches were used in the study to understand the total data analysis provided by the participants via IDI and FGD. As mentioned by Creswell (2018), data analysis is a continuous process that includes asking questions and making interpretations of the data obtained throughout the study. Creswell's model was used in the analysis of the responses of the participants.

The first step is cycle coding, which involves structuring the data gathered. The students' recorded data was transcribed. Next is data reduction which is the process of reducing and organizing transcribed data depending on research questions. The extraneous information received from the participants were removed while ensuring that the points intended by the participants kept intact. Further, the researcher restructured and reanalyzed the data during the second cycle of coding. The recorded interviews were reviewed, patterns among the initial codes were recognized and the process of developing themes followed.

Moreover, the thematic analysis concentrated on identifying, evaluating, and identifying and noting patterns or themes in data. Themes are patterns in data sets that help describe a phenomenon and are connected to a particular research question (Mertens, 2018). The researcher read and reread the transcripts numerous times before undertaking the thematic analysis to become familiar with the data. The data was then organized to generate initial codes. Codes reduced ideas into smaller chunks of meaning. Codes were examined and grouped according to themes. The generated themes were examined, changed, and expanded upon. As emphasized by Creswell, (2017), the researcher will ensure that the topics are consistent and distinct from one another and the identified themes will be defined to determine their significance.

Sequence, Emphasis, and Mixing Procedures

Sequence. The quantitative and qualitative phases were carried out simultaneously. This method allows the findings to be cross-validated, confirmed, and corroborated to ensure that one supported and explained the findings of another.

Emphasis. Both phases were given equal weight because the quantitative and qualitative phases were conducted simultaneously. Therefore, quantitative and qualitative data are equally important in the convergent design.

Mixing Procedure. The quantitative phase involved the collection and analysis of numerical data, while the qualitative phase gathered narratives from public elementary school teachers regarding their experiences of metacognitive awareness, work task motivation, and teaching competence. Integrating the qualitative and quantitative data was crucial in achieving a comprehensive analysis of the research problem. The corroboration analysis, conducted after analyzing both types of data, helped identify commonalities, resolve conflicts, and enhance the understanding of the relationship between metacognitive awareness, work task motivation, and teaching competence among public elementary school teachers.

Ethical Considerations

This pertinent paper was submitted to the UIC-REC and was subjected to the ethics protocol. The researcher assured that this study strictly adhered to the ethics policies and protect human subjects in the pursuit of the study. In short, the researcher considered the principles inherent in the National Ethical Guidelines for Research Involving Human Participants 2022 when doing academic research such as this dissertation. This study adhered to ten ethical considerations guidelines, which are as follows: social value, informed consent, the vulnerability of research participants, risks, benefits, safety, privacy and confidentiality of information, justice, transparency, researcher qualifications, adequacy of facilities, and community involvement.

Social Value. The findings of this study will provide meaningful information to school educators in terms of metacognitive awareness of teaching, teachers' work task motivation, and teaching competence among public elementary teachers. Furthermore, the study's findings will provide feedback to teachers, school administrators, and even policymakers on how to improve teachers' teaching competence and empower teachers to develop knowledge of and have control over how they think and teach by organizing, supervising, assessing, and revising their instructional objectives and delivery strategies in light of their student's needs and the sociocultural environment.

Further, this enables school administrators to identify areas for improvement in terms of quality education and design intervention programs to address the issue to strengthen and improve teachers' teaching competence. As a result, this research aimed to inspire other researchers to do research focusing on the impact of differentiated strategies on teachers' teaching competence. Education's role in skill upgrading and development will be crucial.

More importantly, the findings of this study will be used to deliver critical information to the community, in particular, school administrators and DepEd authorities, significantly at the Division Offices and the Division's hub research library in the Davao Region. To communicate the importance of this endeavor, the findings from this research will predominantly be disseminated via publications online for the large majority of readers such as scholarly journals, research forums, and conferences. The dissemination of the research's findings is its most significant contribution.

Informed Consent. Informed consent is crucial to the study. The researcher explained ahead to the research participants the nature of the data collection and assure them that their identities will be protected. Further, since the participants are teachers, signed consent forms were secured. The researcher let them read and sign the consent forms voluntarily without coercion in any way. As part of this consent, on the other hand, the right to withdraw was included. The researcher let the participants realize that they will certainly have a leeway whether or not to participate in the research at any stage without punishment. Thus, respect for anonymity and confidentiality was highly observed in this study. They were instructed to become acquainted with the study's procedure, methods, and design, as well as their rights as research participants.

Vulnerability of Research Participants. Given that the participants in this survey were older than 18 years old, they were already of legal age to determine whether or not to engage in the study. As such, the researcher secured signed consent forms from them. Additionally, the researcher ensured that the research participants did not suffer any unintentional physical or emotional harm. Also, the researcher made certain that the study participants were not harmed in any manner. And the data acquired for this study were only utilized to produce results that address the research problem. Other than what is specified in the declaration of consent, the participants were not used in any other purposes.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety. There were no high-risk events expected during the conduct of this research. The researcher ensured that the participants' safety was safeguarded throughout the process. Furthermore, beneficence is concerned with doing good to the respondents. According to Creswell (2007), in the 1971 Belmont Report, beneficence is defined more broadly, as an obligation. This was done to maximize potential benefits while minimizing potential risks to the specific research participant. The principle of beneficence requires the researcher to consider the long-term advantages and risks that occur from increased knowledge and the growth of the research's results. Researchers and their institutions must devise strategies to maximize rewards while minimizing risks. To address beneficence, Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) protocols were strictly followed to avoid the spread of COVID-19. Moreover, potential risks such as discomfort, inconvenience, embarrassment, or anxiety of the participants were revealed and explained to them. The researcher guaranteed that all risk mitigation measures were implemented to minimize these potential hazards.

Furthermore, DepEd-Region XI will be informed of the findings and recommendations as compensation for allowing the researcher to carry out the study. The researcher will ensure that the study's results will contribute to the creation of new ideas and will be highly beneficial in crafting projects, programs, and activities that will improve the efficiency and teaching competence of public elementary school teachers in the Davao Region. To optimize the participants' benefits, the researcher compensated them for their time and efforts during the study with tokens of appreciation.

Privacy and Confidentiality. This study adhered to Republic Act No. 10173, generally known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which highlights critical ethical considerations. The following are the ethical considerations in the conduct of the research: participants were not be subjected to harm in any way; participants' dignity was prioritized; full consent was obtained before the study was conducted; participants' privacy was protected; an adequate level of confidentiality of research data was ensured; anonymity of participants was also ensured for their safety; and exaggeration of aims and objectives was avoided; any type of study-related communication was honest and transparent, and any type of misleading information or biased data misrepresentation was avoided.

To ensure data privacy in the study, the researcher only considered participants who signed the informed consent form that contained adequate information about the study. No names were mentioned in any aspect of the study to maintain anonymity and privacy. In addition, proper language usage was observed during the interview. The data gathered and analyzed were utilized solely for this study, and evidence was stored securely in a location known only to the researcher. Furthermore, no information identifying the participants' identities will be shared if this work will be published or presented at any conferences.

Justice. In the Belmont Report in 1971, justice is defined as the equitable distribution of the advantages and risks of taking part in a research study. To ascertain whether certain pools of participants are systematically chosen for reasons other than those directly connected to the research problem being addressed, they must be regularly monitored during the selection process for research participants (Creswell, 2007).

In this study, the researcher made sure that the participants were selected fairly and justly for this survey. Anyone who satisfied the inclusion criteria were viewed as a potential study participant. As a researcher, he ensured that each principle was addressed to protect the rights of each participant. In addition, the researcher surely fostered qualities essential to collaborative work, such as trust, responsibility, mutual respect, and justice, because research usually takes cooperation and coordination among numerous researchers from various disciplines and institutions.

Further, the researcher recognized each participant's involvement as a vital component of the research's overall success was crucial. In all of their endeavors, they received proper credit. Participants in this study were not charged anything to complete the survey

questionnaires or the interview. They received tokens of appreciation for their contributions to the study. Furthermore, the researcher guaranteed that participants were at ease throughout the IDI and FGD sessions. Additionally, the researcher made sure that only their relevant and correct responses were included in the study. Participants were always treated fairly and respectfully during the research to prevent bias.

Moreover, a copy of this research work will be sent to the Schools Division Offices-Planning and Research Department in Region XI so that policymakers will be informed of the study's findings which will eventually benefit the teacherrespondents.

Transparency. This research showed respect to the procedures of transparency by fully disclosing to the participants the existence of this study. Moreover, the researcher informed them that the study is part of the requirements for his doctorate degree and that their being honest with themselves about the answers to the questions they are responding to would be highly appreciated and valued. This study would serve as the gold standard for conducting research and disseminating findings. More importantly, the results of this study will be shared openly with the participants so that they can access the results anytime.

Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured that adequate resources were provided to carry out the research in terms of time, participants, and equipment. Additionally, the researcher was reliable and credible to conduct or supervise the research, and he was aware of his responsibility for the behaviors of the respondents. Furthermore, as a certified researcher, he ensured that he adhered to the research protocol that optimizes the likelihood that the research will achieve its intended goal. Likewise, the researcher consulted his dissertation adviser and other field experts of research promptly to verify the validity and authenticity of the data gathered, as well as the accuracy and soundness of the study's findings. Moreover, the researcher maintained awareness, sensitivity, and humility toward the participants' needs throughout this research.

Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher ensured that the sources he used to collect data and learning materials were ample and readily available so that respondents were at ease filling out the information required for the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the necessary facilities for the study were available and accessible. To ensure a better and more in-depth knowledge of the research, online resources for readings and references were made available. Audio recorders, cameras, computers, printers, and other software programs for data storage and security were prepared and utilized.

Community Involvement. This scholarly research's findings will be shared with the different schools to increase their level of understanding for the improvement of the specific areas in the organization and plan to improve the metacognitive awareness on teaching, teachers' work task motivation, and teaching competence among the public elementary teachers in the Davao Region.

Furthermore, the findings of this study will be used to deliver critical information to the community, particularly school administrators and DepEd authorities. Thus, this would aid and encourage them to acknowledge and urge teachers to be competent in their chosen field to impart vital knowledge to students and to facilitate learning in becoming flexible, creative, and self-directed learners. School administrators would also recognize the necessity for teachers to be adequately qualified and knowledgeable about various teaching techniques to support students with additional educational requirements in grasping learning tasks, self-organizing, and regulating their learning.

More essentially, the outcomes of this research will be disseminated via publications such as scholarly journals, as well as research forums and conferences, to share the relevance of this endeavor. Furthermore, the results of this study will be shared with policymakers to generate ideas, plans, and innovations that will improve teacher effectiveness concerning the difficulties and issues addressed by this research. This could also serve as therapy and motivation for teachers to advance their profession, gain courage and dedication as educators, or even boost their morale.

Results and Discussion

The Status of Metacognitive Awareness of Public Elementary School Teachers

The status of metacognitive awareness of public elementary school teachers as reflected in table has an overall mean of 4.68 described as very high which means that the metacognitive awareness of public elementary school teachers is always manifested. In addition, its minimal standard deviation of .33 shows that the responses of the teachers closely resemble each other.

Declarative Knowledge. The category mean of this domain is 4.78 described as very high. As shown in the table, all items in this category are ranging from 4.75 to 4.80. The item, being aware of the strengths and weaknesses in their teaching has a mean of 4.75. Meanwhile, the item knowing what skills are most important in order to be a good teacher and having control over how well they teach have the same mean of 4.80.

Procedural Knowledge. The category mean of this domain is 4.67 described as very high. As shown in the table, all items in this category are ranging from 4.61 to 4.71. The item, being aware of what teaching techniques they use while they are teaching has a mean of 4.61 described as very high.

Table 1.1. *The Status of Metacognitive Awareness of Public Elementary School Teachers*

	Mean	SD	Description
Declarative Knowledge			
1. being aware of their strengths and weaknesses in their teaching.	4.75	.442	Very High
2. knowing what skills are most important in order to be a good teacher.	4.80	.40	Very High
3. having control over how well they teach.	4.80	.42	Very High
4. knowing what they are expected to teach.	4.77	.42	Very High
Category Mean	4.78	.32	Very High
Procedural Knowledge			
1. trying to use teaching techniques that worked in the past.	4.64	.62	Very High
2. having a specific reason for choosing each teaching technique they use in class.	4.71	.46	Very High
3. being aware of what teaching techniques they use while they are teaching.	4.61	.60	Very High
4. using helpful teaching techniques automatically.	4.71	.48	Very High
Category Mean	4.67	.42	Very High
Conditional Knowledge			
1. using their strengths to compensate for their weaknesses in their teaching.	4.65	.59	Very High
2. being able to motivate themselves to teach when they really need to teach.	4.79	.41	Very High
3. using different teaching techniques depending on the situation.	4.74	.48	Very High
4. knowing when each teaching technique they use will be most effective.	4.69	.55	Very High
Category Mean	4.72	.38	Very High
Planning			
1. pacing themselves while they are teaching to have enough time.	4.64	.62	Very High
2. setting their specific teaching goals before they start teaching.	4.68	.51	Very High
3. asking themselves questions about the teaching materials they are going to use.	4.63	.58	Very High
4. organizing their time to best accomplish their teaching goals.	4.75	.44	Very High
Category Mean	4.67	.41	Very High
Monitoring			
1. asking themselves periodically if they meet their teaching goals while they are teaching.	4.65	.61	Very High
2. finding themselves assessing how useful their teaching techniques are while they are teaching.	4.74	.44	Very High
4. checking regularly to what extent their students comprehend the topic while they are teaching.	4.56	.61	Very High
4. asking themselves questions about how well they are doing while they are teaching.	4.57	.72	Very High
Category Mean	4.63	.44	Very High
Evaluating			
1. asking themselves how well they have accomplished their teaching goals once they are finished.	4.46	.78	Very High
2. asking themselves if they could have used different techniques after each teaching experience.	4.72	.56	Very High
3. asking themselves after teaching a point how they taught to teach more effectively next time.	4.66	.51	Very High
4. asking themselves if they have considered all possible techniques after teaching a point.	4.67	.49	Very High
Category Mean	4.62	.45	Very High
Overall Mean	4.68	.33	Very High

Meanwhile, the items, having a specific reason for choosing each teaching technique they use in class and using helpful teaching techniques automatically have the same mean rating of 4.71 described as very high.

Conditional Knowledge. This domain has a category mean of 4.72 described as very high with item mean ratings that range from 4.65 to 4.79, The item, using their strengths to compensate for their weaknesses in their teaching has a mean of 4.65 described as very high,

while the item, being able to motivate themselves to teach when they really need to teach has a mean of 4.79 described as very high.

Planning. The category mean of this domain is 4.67 described as very high. As shown in the table, all items in this category are ranging from 4.63 to 4.75. The item, asking themselves questions about the teaching materials they are going to use has a mean 4.63 described as very high. Meanwhile, the item organizing their time to best accomplish their teaching goals has a mean of 4.75 described as very high.

Monitoring. The domain, monitoring has category mean rating of 4.63 described as very high. The item mean rating ranges from 4.56 to 4.74. Specifically, the item, checking regularly to what extent their students comprehend the topic while they are teaching has a mean of 4.56 described as very high while the item finding themselves assessing how useful their teaching techniques are while they are teaching has a mean rating of 4.74 described as very high.

Evaluating. This domain has a category mean of 4.62 described as very high. The item mean ratings of this domain range from 4.46 to 4.72. On one hand, the item, asking themselves how well they have accomplished their teaching goals once they had finished has a mean rating of 4.46 described as very high. On the other hand, asking themselves if they could have used different techniques after each teaching experience has a mean rating of 4.72 described as very high.

The Status of Work Task Motivation of Public Elementary School Teachers

It is shown in Table 1.2 that in totality, the status of work task motivation of public elementary school teachers has an overall mean of 4.55 described as very high. Considering the degrees of dispersion in this variable, standard deviation is .36 indicating that the responses are clustered around the mean.

Table 1.2. *The Status of Work Task Motivation of Public Elementary School Teachers*

	Mean	SD	Description
Intrinsic Motivation			
1. finding it pleasant to carry out their tasks.	4.66	.57	Very High
2. having tasks that are interesting to do.	4.68	.56	Very High
3. liking the tasks, they are doing.	4.67	.54	Very High
Category Mean	4.67	.46	Very High
Identified Regulation			
1. considering it important for them to carry out their tasks.	4.66	.53	Very High
2. allowing them to attain work objectives that they consider important when they do their tasks.	4.59	.61	Very High
3. finding their tasks important for the academic success of their students.	4.55	.70	Very High
Category Mean	4.60	.54	Very High
Introjected Motivation			
1. being guilty if their tasks are unfulfilled.	4.59	.65	Very High
2. feeling unhappy about being inactive.	4.55	.70	Very High
3. disliking when doing their tasks makes them feel bad.	4.62	.55	Very High
Category Mean	4.59	.54	Very High
External Regulation			
1. having work demands for them to do.	4.60	.56	Very High
2. obliging them to do their tasks.	4.60	.58	Very High
3. being paid to do their tasks.	4.64	.55	Very High
Category Mean	4.62	.47	Very High
Amotivation			
1. feeling that they know, and have always seen the relevance of carrying out their task.	3.99	.66	High
2. being used to know why they always do their tasks, and they still see the reason.	4.57	.58	Very High
3. seeing the purpose of what they are doing.	4.23	.58	Very High
Category Mean	4.26	.38	Very High
Overall Mean	4.55	.36	Very High

Intrinsic Motivation. This first domain of work task motivation was rated by the public elementary school teachers with category mean rating of 4.67 described as very high. The item in this category obtained mean ratings within the range of 4.66 to 4.68. Particularly, the item, finding it pleasant to carry out their tasks has a mean of 4.66 described as very high while the item having their tasks as interesting to do has a mean rating of 4.68 described as very high.

Identified Regulation. This domain reveals a category mean of 4.60 described as very high. In particular, the mean ratings in this category are ranging from 4.55 to 4.66. Looking at the items, it shows that the item, finding their tasks important for the academic success of their students has a mean of 4.55 described as very high while the item, considering it important for them to carry out their tasks has a mean of 4.66 also described as very high.

Introjected Motivation. This domain of work task motivation was rated by the public elementary school teachers with category mean rating of 4.59 described as very high. The item in this category obtained mean ratings within the range of 4.55 to 4.62. Particularly, the item, feeling unhappy about being inactive has a mean of 4.55 described as very high while the item disliking when doing their tasks makes them feel has a mean rating of 4.62 described as very high.

External Regulation. This domain reveals a category mean of 4.62 described as very high. In particular, the mean ratings in this category ranges from 4.60 to 4.64. It shows that the items, having work demands for them to do them and obliging them to do their tasks has a mean of 4.60 described as very high while the item, being paid to do their tasks has a mean of 4.64 described as very high.

Amotivation. This domain of work task motivation was rated by the public elementary school teachers with a category mean rating of 4.26 described as very high. The item in this category obtained mean ratings within the range of 3.99 to 4.57. Particularly, the item, feeling that they know, and have always seen the relevance of carrying out their task has a mean of 3.99 described as high while the item being used to know why they always do their tasks, and they still see the reason has a mean rating of 4.57 described as very high.

The Status of Teaching Competence of Public Elementary School Teachers

It is shown in Table 1.3 that the status of teaching competence of public elementary school teachers has an overall mean rating of 4.62 described as very high. Considering the degrees of dispersion in this variable, the standard deviation is .24 denotes that the response ratings of the teachers are clustered around the mean.

Planning Skills. This domain reveals a category mean of 4.61 described as very high. In particular, the mean ratings in this category ranges from 4.56 to 4.65. The item selecting audio-visual resources which are suitable, adequate, and needed to achieve the objectives and fit to the learners and the subject has a mean of 4.56 describe as very high while the item, having the objectives of the lesson appropriate, clearly stated relevant to the content, adequate, and attainable has a mean of 4.65 described as very high.

Table 1.3. *The Status of Teaching Competence of Public Elementary School Teachers*

	Mean	SD	Description
Planning Skills			
1. having the objectives of the lesson appropriate, clearly stated relevant to the content, adequate, and attainable.	4.65	.67	Very High
2. selecting appropriately, relevant, and adequate content with respect to the objectives of the lesson, and accurate.	4.61	.53	Very High
3. properly selecting and organizing the content with logical continuity and psychological organization.	4.60	.53	Very High
4. selecting audio-visual resources which are suitable, adequate, and needed to achieve the objectives and fit to the learners and the subject.	4.56	.51	Very High
Category Mean	4.61	.43	Very High
Presentation Skills			
1. effectively introducing the lesson, and preparing intellectually and emotionally the learners to receive it using appropriate tools and techniques, continuity in statements and questions, and the utilization of prior knowledge.	4.61	.49	Very High
2. asking questions that were appropriate, well structured, properly put, adequate in number, and made learners participate.	4.52	.57	Very High
3. providing probing questions that helped learners develop critical awareness by motivating them to seek out more information, refocus, redirect, and increase their critical awareness.	4.68	.53	Very High
4. giving clear, interrelated, and meaningful statements that created sets and generated conclusions, had relevance, continuity, proper vocabulary, fluency, and no vague words helped explain concepts and principles.	4.64	.54	Very High
5. illustrating the concepts and principles with the help of appropriate examples through appropriate media (verbal and non-verbal): simply relevant to the content and interest level of learners.	4.66	.49	Very High

6. capturing the attention of the learners and holding by a variety of cues, including postures, motions, gestures, changing speech patterns, focusing, changing interaction styles, pausing, and oral-visual switching.	4.65	.52	Very High
7. using deliberate silence and nonverbal cues to increase learners' participation.	4.55	.50	Very High
8. responding and initiating the participation of learners were encouraged using verbal and nonverbal reinforcements.	4.65	.48	Very High
9. having appropriate speed of presentation of ideas which are matched with the rate of learners' understanding with proper budgeting of time.	4.52	.51	Very High
10. initiating learners' participation in the classroom by responding to their teacher, giving their idea and reacting to others' ideas.	4.48	.58	Very High
11. having blackboard work that is good: legible, neat, appropriate of content written, and adequate.	4.62	.48	Very High
Category Mean	4.60	.32	Very High
Closing Skills			
1. summarizing the lesson's important points, past knowledge and current knowledge connected, providing chances for applying current knowledge presented, and knowledge connected to future learning.	4.50	.51	Very High
2. giving assignments to the learners which are appropriate, suited to individual differences, relevant to the content taught, and adequate.	4.75	.44	Very High
Category Mean	4.63	.40	Very High
Evaluation Skills			
1. having evaluation procedures that are appropriate, relevant to the objectives, valid, reliable, objective, and the learners' progress toward the lesson's objectives are assessed.	4.69	.46	Very High
2. diagnosing the learners' difficulties in understanding a concept or principle by step-by-step questioning and undertaking suitable remedial measures.	4.66	.47	Very High
Category Mean	4.68	.35	Very High
Managerial Skills			
1. acknowledging learners who are present as those who are absent, rewarding good attendance while discouraging bad attendance, and verifying good attendance with questions and nonverbal cues.	4.68	.47	Very High
2. maintaining classroom discipline in the class by having learners follow the teacher's instructions	4.52	.50	Very High
Category Mean	4.60	.41	Very High
Overall Mean	4.62	.24	Very High

Presentation Skills. This domain has a category mean of 4.60 described as very high. Notably, the items in this category obtained mean ratings which are ranging from 4.48 to 4.68. The item, initiating learners' participation in the classroom by responding to their teacher, giving their idea and reacting to others' ideas has a mean of 4.48 described as very high. Meanwhile the item, providing probing questions that helped learners develop critical awareness by motivating them to seek out more information, refocus, redirect, and increase their critical awareness has a mean of 4.68 described as very high.

Closing Skills. This domain reveals a category mean of 4.63 described as very high. In particular, the mean ratings in this category are ranging from 4.50 to 4.75. The item summarizing the lesson's important points, past knowledge and current knowledge connected, presenting chances for applying current knowledge, and knowledge connected to future learning has a mean of 4.50 describe as very high while the item, giving assignment to the learners which are appropriate, suited to individual differences, relevant to the content taught, and adequate has a mean of 4.75 described as very high.

Evaluation Skills. This domain has a category mean of 4.68 described as very high. Notably, the items in this category obtained mean ratings ranging from 4.66 to 4.69. The item, diagnosing the learners' difficulties in understanding a concept or principle by step-by-step questioning and undertaking suitable remedial measures has a mean of 4.66 described as very high. Meanwhile the item, having evaluation procedures that are appropriate, relevant to the objectives, valid, reliable, objective, and the learners' progress toward the lesson's objectives are assessed has a mean of 4.69 described as very high.

Managerial Skills. This domain has a category mean of 4.60 described as very high. Notably, the items in this category obtained mean ratings ranging from 4.52 to 4.68. The item, maintaining classroom discipline in the class by having learners follow the teacher's instructions has a mean of 4.52 described as very high. Meanwhile, the item, acknowledging learners who are present as those who are absent, rewarding good attendance while discouraging bad attendance, and verifying good attendance with questions and nonverbal cues has a mean of 4.68 described as very high.

Significance of the Influence of Metacognitive Awareness, and Work Task Motivation towards Teaching Competence of Public Elementary School Teachers

Table 2 shows the results of the multiple regression analysis which is set at level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ (two-tailed). On the one hand, the standardized beta coefficient of metacognitive awareness is $-.08$, with t -statistics of -1.56 and p -value of $.08$ which is greater than the $.05$ level of significance. This indicates that in individual capacity, the metacognitive awareness of public elementary school teachers is not a significant predictor of teaching competence of public elementary school teachers. It means that for every unit increase in the status of metacognitive awareness of public elementary school teachers, there is a corresponding decrease of $.08$ units which is not significant in their teaching competence.

On the other hand, the standardized beta coefficient of work task motivation of public elementary school teachers is $.18$, with a t -statistics of 3.28 and $p = .00$ which is less than $.05$ level of significance. This result indicates that work task motivation is a significant predictor of teaching competence of public elementary school teachers. It means that for every unit increase in the status of work task motivation of public elementary school teachers corresponds to an increase of $.18$ in their teaching competence.

Further, the F -ratio in Table 2 indicates whether the overall regression model, which is the combined effect of metacognitive awareness and work task motivation as predictors of teaching competence, is a good fit for the data in this study.

Table 2. *Significance of the Influence of the Metacognitive Awareness and Work Task Motivation towards Teaching Competence of Public Elementary School Teachers*

Predictors	Standardized Beta Coefficient	t	p-value	Remarks
Metacognitive Awareness	-.08	-1.56	.08	Not Significant
Work Task Motivation	.18	3.28	.00	Significant
Combined Influence of Predictors				
Metacognitive Awareness and Work Task Motivation				
R	.163			
R ²	.027			
F	5.417			
P	.005			Significant

The results reveal that metacognitive awareness and work task motivation significantly predict teaching competence of public elementary school teachers as shown in the result of $F(2, 397) = 5.42, p < .05$. Therefore, the regression model is a good fit of the empirical data of this study.

Furthermore, the R -square value reflects the proportion of variance in the teaching competence of the public elementary school teachers that can be explained by their metacognitive awareness and work task motivation. The R -square value is reported at $.03$ indicating that three percent in the variability of teaching competence of public elementary school teachers can be explained by the combined influence of the predictors, metacognitive awareness, and work task motivation. The remaining 97 percent is attributable to the unexplained variance, or other factors not included in this study.

Profile of the Participants

Table 3 reveals the profile of the participants involved in the second strand of this study. The data discloses certain information like the participant's number, IDI number, sex, the study group mode of online communication, and the location. As shown in Table 3 there were 17 participants who were purposively selected by the researcher to make clarifications for the qualitative strand of this mixed methods study.

Table 3. *Profile of the Participants*

Participant No.	Codes of the Participants	Sex	Data Source Group	Division
01	IDI P1	F	IDI	Davao City
02	IDI P2	F	IDI	Davao City
03	IDI P3	F	IDI	Mati City
04	IDI P4	F	IDI	Mati City
05	IDI P5	M	IDI	Panabo City
06	IDI P6	F	IDI	Panabo City
07	IDI P7	F	IDI	Tagum City
08	IDI P8	M	IDI	Tagum City
09	IDI P9	M	IDI	Davao Del Norte

10	IDI P10	F	IDI	Davao Del Norte
11	FGD P1	F	FGD	Davao Oriental
12	FGD P2	F	FGD	Davao Oriental
13	FGD P3	M	FGD	Davao Oriental
14	FGD P4	F	FGD	Davao Oriental
15	FGD P5	F	FGD	Davao Oriental
16	FGD P6	M	FGD	Davao Oriental
17	FGD P7	F	FGD	Davao Oriental

Furthermore, as indicated in the table above there were 10 IDI participants which are composed of three male teachers and seven female teachers. In addition, a total of seven FGD participants were also purposively selected that are composed of two male-teachers and five female-teachers. All participants fit in the inclusion criteria as informants of the study. The participants were asked to give their lived experiences as regards their teaching competence.

The Lived Experiences of Public Elementary School Teachers as regards their Teaching Competence

Table 4 below shows the lived experiences of the participants as regards their teaching competence. The data gathered through IDI and FGD were transcribed, coded, grouped, and organized into themes. In this particular research question on the lived experiences of public elementary school teachers regarding their teaching competence, five essential themes emerged and these are; appropriateness of learning-task designs, mindfulness of teaching-learning strategies, established teacher presence, higher-level thinking skills reinforcement, and discipline and morale maintenance.

Table 4. The Lived Experiences of Public Elementary School Teachers as regards their Teaching Competence

<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Appropriateness of learning-task designs	Planning of strategies to be used in class Localizing and contextualizing strategies Providing examples that the students can relate to Choosing the appropriate teaching styles and learning materials Setting SMART objectives
Mindfulness of teaching-learning strategies	Assessing themselves on what are needed to improve in teaching Reflecting on effective teaching strategies for the learners Weighing things that work and do not work for the students
Established teacher presence	Ensuring that the learners listen and find the lesson interesting Making sure that they are visible and audible enough for the learners Engaging the students in the discussion Engaging students in various group or individual tasks
Higher-level thinking skills reinforcement	Connecting prior knowledge to new ideas Building anticipation for the next lesson Raising questions and encouraging pupils to ask clarifications Encouraging students to ask questions Adeptness in the art of questioning
Discipline and morale maintenance	Firmness on the imposition of class rules Setting boundaries and being consistent Setting classroom standards Providing reinforcements for exemplary behavior Giving simple rewards.

Appropriateness of Learning-Task Designs. The first theme that emerged from the responses of the participants is appropriateness of learning-task designs. The participants shared that the teachers should do the necessary planning and crafting of appropriate learning activities that ought to be implemented during the presentation of the lesson specifically to plan the effective strategies to be used in class, localize and contextualize the strategies, provide examples which the students can relate to, and choosing the appropriate teaching styles and learning materials. These are evident in the words of the participants which are as follows:

- I always do planning sir especially what appropriate approaches that I am going to use in a specific objective... (IDI P3) (IDI P4)*
- So, if ever there are no available learning materials, sir, I localize and contextualize my strategies so they can easily understand. (IDI P7)*
- I am preparing the content of the lesson and the teaching materials and evaluation tools that will be implemented for my evaluation. (IDI P9) (FGD P4)*
- I also make sure that I am using relevant teaching and learning activities to ensure the achievement of the set goals for students. (FGD P1) (FGD P5)*
- I am also ensuring that the objectives of my lesson plan must be SMART... also considering the diversity of my students. The lesson should be done with achievable objectives. (FGD P3, FGD P4, FGD P6)*

Mindfulness of Teaching-Learning Strategies. The second theme that emerged from the responses of the participants is mindfulness of teaching-learning strategies. Most of the participants believed that teachers should learn with an open mind. These are mentioned when

the participants elaborated that the metacognitive awareness of public elementary school teachers help assess themselves on what they need to improve in teaching, reflect on what teaching strategies and delivery of instruction are effective for the learners, and weigh things that work and do not work the students. These are evident in the following statements;

It helps me reflect on what teaching strategies and delivery of instruction are effective for my learners...It gives me a better understanding on my learner's perspective in learning... (IDI P1) (IDI P2)

It allows me to know myself, both my strengths and weaknesses...sir, I became aware of who I am and how can I improve my way of teaching... (IDI P5) (IDI P3)

It enables me to realize what's lacking and the mistakes in my teaching. With that, I can still improve myself... especially in terms of strategies. (FGD P1) (FGD P3)

It contributes in my teaching competence to evaluate myself if I am still effective to my students or not. (FGD P4)

It allows me to weigh things that work and those that do not. This means that I will be able to use different techniques in different situations...thus improving the quality of my teaching skills. (FGD P5)

Established Teacher Presence. The third theme that emerged from the participants' responses is established teacher presence. This was highlighted when participants emphasized the importance of teachers establishing a strong presence in the classroom. Teachers need to ensure that the learners are engaged and find the lessons interesting. Additionally, they should make themselves visible enough for the learners and audible enough for the students to hear. Participants revealed that:

I make sure that my learners are listening and find the lesson interesting. (IDI P1) (IDI P4)

I will ensure sir that I can capture the attention of my learners so that they will really listen and I will not have difficulty introducing the lesson to them. (IDI P5)

I always make it sure that I am visible enough for my learners to see and audible enough for them to hear me. (IDI P7) (IDI P8)

I make sure that the students actively engage in the discussion. (FGD P2)

I must possess good communication skills so that students will listen to me... (FGD P5)

I keep my presentation interesting to my learners so that they will engage themselves in various group or individual tasks. (FGD P7)

Higher-Level Thinking Skills Reinforcement. Another essential theme that emerged from the responses of the participants is higher-level thinking skills reinforcement. Most participants agreed that individuals should strive for higher-level thinking skills. These were highlighted by participants when they elaborated that teachers raise questions and encourage students to ask for clarifications, encourage students to ask, and use the art of questioning. This is reflected in the following statements:

I create a link to new ideas and build anticipation for the next lesson. (IDI P3)

I am asking questions and connecting their answers from one lesson to another. (IDI P1) (IDI P7)

Raising questions and encouraging pupils to ask clarifications are some of the things I used to do in my classroom. (IDI P2)

I encourage them to ask questions and queries sir if there is something that bothers in their mind. (IDI P8) (IDI P7)

I give oral or written questions sir that stimulate critical thinking depending on the specific objective we have on that day. (IDI P9)

Discipline and Morale Maintenance. Another essential theme that emerged from the responses of the participants is discipline and morale maintenance. Most participants agreed that teachers should be firm on the rules in class, defining boundaries and being consistent, setting classroom standards, setting boundaries, rewarding well-behaved students, and giving basic prizes.

These are evident in the words of the participants which are as follows:

I manage them with authority and firm decision but I lead them like their companion... firm on the rules I gave to my class. (IDI P1) (IDI P2)

Setting boundaries and being consistent has also been part of my management. (IDI P3) (FGD P6)

I remind my learners to follow instructions and encourage my learners to participate. (IDI P7)

I provide rewards for my behaved students. (IDI P8)

I give positive management of my students' behavior. (IDI P9)

I explain clearly or explicitly to my class the standards that we have in the classroom... rules and regulations that we have must be practical and consistently reinforced. (IDI P10) (IDI P4)

Role of the Experiences that Shaped the Beliefs, Attitudes, and Commitment of Public Elementary School Teachers Pertaining to their Teaching Competence

Table 5 below shows the insights shared by the participants as regards the beliefs, attitudes, and commitment of public elementary school teachers pertaining their teaching competence. Based on the IDI and FGD conducted, answers were transcribed, coded, grouped, and organized into themes and the resulting themes include teaching with a heart, thoughtfulness in pedagogy, and steadfast in teaching.

Table 5. *Role of the Experiences that Shaped the Belief, Attitude, and Commitment of Public Elementary School Teachers Pertaining to their Teaching Competence*

Essential Themes	Core Ideas
	On Beliefs
Teaching with a heart	Integrate feelings in teaching Teach students not just their intellectual aspects but the most important thing is the heart of the learners Being sensitive towards the students Responsive to the needs of the learners Being aware of their strengths and weaknesses of students
	On Attitude
Thoughtfulness in pedagogy	Every day in school is another opportunity to learn. Creativity in the preparation of instructional activities and materials Teachers should not really stop learning Flexibility in designing classroom activities Versatility in teaching
Steadfast in teaching	Having passion for work Being motivated each day Being dedicated and persevering in teaching Being resolute in teaching Being an efficient and effective teacher

Teaching with a Heart. When participants were interviewed about their beliefs, pertaining their teaching competence, participants emphasized that teachers must integrate feelings in teaching and teach students not just their intellectual aspects but the most important thing is the heart of the learners. Being sensitive towards the students, responsive to the needs of the learners, and being aware of their strengths and weaknesses of students are highly regarded in teaching. These are evident in the following statements;

Let us not limit ourselves to teaching what is in our minds. It is also important to put our hearts. (IDI P2)

Teach students not just their intellectual aspects but the most important thing is the heart of the learners. (IDI P3)

Shape the heart of the pupils how to integrate feelings upon teaching. (IDI P5) (FGD P4)

I must be aware of the strengths and weaknesses of my pupils. (IDI P10)

Be a teacher who is responsive to the needs of the learners. (FGD P2)

Being sensitive towards my students, it may be about their belief, cultural background, cognitive level, religious belief or learning preferences. (FGD P6)

Thoughtfulness in Pedagogy. On the attitudes of public elementary school teachers pertaining to their teaching competence, participants focused on how they demonstrate flexibility in planning classroom activities and versatility in teaching. For the participants, flexibility in designing classroom activities and versatility in teaching are significant aspects of a teacher's pedagogical creativity.

This is reflected in the following statements:

I have to become flexible in designing classroom activities. Every day in school is another learning experience for me and my learners. (IDI P1) (IDI P4) (IDI P5) (FGD P7)

I must be versatile or let me say flexible in my teaching. (IDI P6)

It allows me to achieve things that I consider most important... teachers should not really stop learning because everything in this world does not stop changing. (IDI P3)

I always grab the opportunity to learn skills and always employ willingness at every chance or opportunity that comes along the way. (IDI P8)

We have to discover more strategies to be incorporated in designing our lesson. (FGD P2) (FGD P5)

Steadfast in Teaching. Another essential theme that emerged from the responses of the participants about their commitment pertaining their teaching competence is dedication. Most participants agreed that teachers should have passion for work and always be motivated each day. Being resolute in teaching and being an efficient and effective teacher are highly esteemed qualities in the field of education. These are evident in the words of the participants which are as follows:

Work as much as possible, do what you can do, accept what you need to experience and go out of your comfort zone for your

improvement. (IDI P2)

Have passion for my work because it will lighten the burden and struggles I may face in the field of teaching. (IDI P4)

It deepens my passion and love in teaching...always feeling motivated each day. (IDI P5)

It helps me gets focus and concentration on the job... I should have dedication and perseverance...being resolute in teaching makes me a competent teacher. (IDI 9) (FGD P1)

It allows me to have the assurance that I can be an efficient and effective teacher and facilitator of learning. (FGD P5)

Data Integration on the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

Table 6 below shows the joint /combined display of the salient quantitative and qualitative findings of metacognitive awareness, work task motivation, and teaching competence of public elementary school teachers in Region XI. Table 6 has four columns which consist of the first column for the aspect of focal points of the study followed by the second and third columns for quantitative and qualitative findings, and the last column is the nature of the integration and its function.

The merging analysis focuses on the nature of data integration which gives a description of the merger of quantitative and qualitative findings.

Table 6. Joint Display of the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

<i>Focal Point</i>	<i>Quantitative Findings</i>	<i>Qualitative Findings</i>	<i>Nature of Data Integration</i>
Metacognitive Awareness	Table 1.1 on the Status of Metacognitive Awareness of Public Elementary School Teachers under Planning specifically organizing their time with a mean of 4.75 (.44) setting their specific teaching goals with a mean of 4.68 (SD=.51)	Table 4 in Lived Experiences of Public Elementary School Teachers as regards their Teaching Competence with Theme Appropriate learning-task designs	Merging-Converging
	Table 1.1 on the Status of Metacognitive Awareness of Public Elementary School Teachers under Procedural knowledge specifically, in having a specific reason (Mean=4.71, SD=.46), being aware of what teaching techniques (Mean=4.61, SD=.60), and using helpful teaching techniques (Mean=4.71, SD=.48).	Table 4 in Lived Experiences of Public Elementary School Teachers as regards their Teaching Competence with theme Appropriate learning-task designs	Merging-Converging
	Table 1.1 on the Status of Metacognitive Awareness of Public Elementary School Teachers under Declarative knowledge with a category mean of 4.78 (SD=.32)	Table 4 in Lived Experiences of Public Elementary School Teachers as regards their Teaching Competence with theme Mindfulness of teaching-learning strategies	Merging-Converging
Work Task Motivation	Table 1.2 on the Status of Work Task Motivation of Public Elementary School Teachers under Intrinsic Motivation specifically in liking the tasks with a mean of 4.67 (SD=.54).	Table 4 in Lived Experiences of Public Elementary School Teachers as regards their Teaching Competence with theme Mindfulness of teaching-learning strategies	Merging-Converging
Teaching Competence	Table 1.3 on the Status of Teaching Competence of Public Elementary School Teachers under Presentation skills specifically in capturing attention of learners (Mean= 4.65, SD=.52), and using deliberate silence (Mean= 4.55, SD=.50). initiating learners' participation with a mean of 4.48 (SD=.58).	Table 4 in Lived Experiences of Public Elementary School Teachers as regards their Teaching Competence with theme Established teacher presence	Merging-Converging
	Table 1.3 on the Status of Teaching Competence of Public Elementary School Teachers under Presentation skills specifically in giving clear, interrelated, and higher-level thinking skills meaningful statements with a mean of 4.64 (SD=.54).	Table 4 in Lived Experiences of Public Elementary School Teachers as regards their Teaching competence with the theme of reinforcement.	Merging-Converging

	Table 1.3 on the Status of Teaching Competence of Public Elementary School Teachers under Presentation skills specifically in asking questions (Mean=4.52, SD=.57), and providing probing questions (Mean=4.68, SD=.53).	
	Table 1.3 on the Status of Teaching Competence of Public Elementary School Teachers under Closing skills with a category mean of 4.63 (SD=.40)	Merging-Converging
	Table 1.3 on the Status of Teaching Competence of Public Elementary School Teachers under Managerial skills specifically in acknowledging learners with a mean of 4.68 (SD=.47).	Merging-Converging
Significance of the Influence of the Metacognitive Awareness and Work Task Motivation towards Teaching Competence	Table 2 on the Significance of the Influence of the Metacognitive Awareness and Work Task Motivation towards Teaching Competence specifically a p-value of .00	Merging-Converging
	Table 5 Role of the Experiences that Shaped the Attitudes of the Public Elementary School Teachers Pertaining to their Teaching Competence with a theme Thoughtfulness in pedagogy	
	Table 5 Role of the Experiences that Shaped the Commitment of Public Elementary School Teachers Pertaining to their Teaching Competence with a theme Steadfast in teaching	

Merging-Converging. The following focal points have their findings which consist of data integration that is merging-converging:

For the focal point of metacognitive awareness, the category, Planning has an item specifically in organizing their time to best accomplish their teaching goals has obtained an average of 4.75 which is described as very high and when merged to qualitative results, converged with the essential theme Appropriateness of Learning-Task Designs. For the same category of Planning, specifically on item 2 about setting their specific teaching goals before they start teaching with a mean of 4.68 which is described as very high. The findings of the data integration surfaced in the qualitative results, which are attributed to the essential theme leads to the Appropriateness of learning-task designs

For the category, Procedural Knowledge, item 2 having a specific reason for choosing each teaching technique they use in class which has a rating of 4.71 described as very high. Additionally, item 3 being aware of what teaching techniques they use while they are teaching with has a mean rating of 4.61 described as very high. Further, item 4 using helpful teaching techniques automatically has a mean rating of 4.71 described as very high. When merged with the qualitative results, it was found to be converging with the essential theme of Appropriateness of learning-task designs.

For the category, Declarative Knowledge, items being aware of the strengths and weaknesses in their teaching, knowing what skills are most important in order to be a good teacher, having control over how well they teach, and knowing what they are expected to teach has a category mean of 4.78 described as very high. When merged with the qualitative results, it was found to be converging with the essential theme of Mindfulness of teaching-learning strategies. Another focal point, work task motivation, where it still has a converging nature when quantitative and qualitative results were merged. For the category Intrinsic Motivation item 3 liking the tasks, they are doing had a rating of 4.67 and a description of very high directly converge with qualitative data with the essential theme Mindfulness of teaching-learning strategies.

Another focal point, teaching competence, the category, Presentation Skills, items 6 and 7, in capturing the attention of the learners and holding by a variety of cues, including postures, motions, gestures, changing speech patterns, focusing, changing interaction styles, pausing, and oral-visual switching and using deliberate silence and nonverbal cues to increase learners' participation with ratings of M=4.65 and M=4.55 both described as very high and converged with qualitative results with the essential theme Established teacher presence.

The Status of Metacognitive Awareness of Public Elementary School Teachers

The result of this study reveals that the status of metacognitive awareness of public elementary school teachers is very high. This implies that the metacognitive awareness is always manifested among public elementary school teachers in Region XI. This suggests that the teachers consistently demonstrate an understanding and application of metacognitive strategies in their teaching practices. Their high level of metacognitive awareness reflects their ability to reflect upon and regulate their thinking processes, which can positively impact student learning and achievement.

This finding conforms with the study of Karimi and Ziaabadi (2019) which disclosed that teacher metacognition plays a well-defined

role in classroom practices and therefore, students get highly engaged in the classrooms with teachers who are more metacognitively aware. This relationship was also investigated by Prytula (2012) who came up with almost the same findings.

Further, this finding is in consonance with result of the study of Palantis et al. (2018) who discovered that the levels of metacognitive awareness among teachers are high at ninety-three percent (93%). Apart from that, the results showed no significant differences by gender, age, teaching experience, academic qualification, and the subject of teaching among primary school teachers. Further, the overall findings stated that teachers who have a higher level of metacognitive awareness can produce students with good academic achievement. Many researchers have viewed that metacognitive awareness about teaching makes a teacher think dynamically and strategically towards his regular teaching process. According to Balcikanli (2011), metacognitive awareness in teaching plays an accelerating element in the whole teaching-learning process. More so, Ozcan's (2007) study revealed that metacognitively aware teachers could use some strategies to improve the students' awareness of metacognition.

Additionally, this result supports the study of Avila and Baetiong (2012), based on the findings of the study, metacognitive strategies caused a positive effect on teachers' teaching performance. The findings further proved the need for teachers to know more about metacognitive strategies and to utilize them in teaching in order to provide sufficient opportunities for students to be actively and deliberately involved in their own learning process. As learners need to learn how to learn, teachers need to learn how to teach and to facilitate the learning process. Although learning is certainly part of human experiences, conscious effort to develop skills in self-directed learning and in strategy use must be sharpened through the use of metacognitive strategies.

Additionally, the result of the study is congruent to the study of Bulut (2018) who found that both pre-school and classroom teachers had high levels of awareness, which is consistent with previous research by Bars (2016) and Batdi (2016). More so, the finding of this study is parallel to the study of Batdi (2016) who also found that teachers had high levels of metacognitive awareness. Additionally, Wilson and Bai (2010) stated that teachers with a strong grasp of metacognitive knowledge can teach metacognitive thinking strategies to their students, leading to improved academic success. Additionally, Aktag (2017) suggested that teachers with high metacognitive awareness create a positive effect in education, while Doğan (2004) found that they enable students to be more successful in the learning process. Therefore, it is important to support teachers in developing their metacognition and understanding of metacognition instruction. Also, Ozturk (2017) recommends that teachers be educated in metacognitive awareness so they can effectively incorporate it into their teaching practices.

Declarative Knowledge. The result of this study proved that this dimension was rated as very high by public elementary school teachers and implied that the declarative knowledge of public elementary school teachers is always manifested. This indicates that this knowledge includes anything that a teacher thinks to be written, speakable, or explicable wherein they are skilled at organizing knowledge and conscious of their intellectual talents and weaknesses of what they are expected to teach and knowing what skills are most important in order for them to be a good teacher.

The result of the study supports the research of Sugiharto et al. (2018) which revealed that if a person has a high level of declarative knowledge, their procedural knowledge and conditional knowledge levels will also be high; there is no a significant difference among the three. The findings of the study suggest that declarative knowledge involves what one knows about oneself, the characteristics of existing tasks, and the nature of strategies. Declarative knowledge, on the other hand, is knowledge about anything (Azevedo & Aleven, 2013), including what one understands, how or when to learn, and what influences the educational process (Young & Fry, 2012). Declarative knowledge is concerned with an individual's perceptions about their cognitive capacities and the external factors affecting their performances (Backer et al., 2011).

Procedural Knowledge. The result of this study proved that this dimension was rated very high and implied that the metacognitive awareness of public elementary school teachers in terms of procedural knowledge is always manifested. This demonstrates that public elementary school teachers know how to use strategies, they are trying to use teaching techniques that worked in the past, have a specific reason for choosing each teaching technique they use in class, are aware of what teaching techniques they use while they are teaching and using helpful teaching techniques automatically.

The result is congruent with the study of Saks et al. (2021) the findings of which revealed that procedural knowledge, being predominantly teacher centered, mostly appears through experience and reflections on the teaching practice that guides them. It also appeared that the intervention focusing on advancing procedural knowledge among teachers advanced their declarative knowledge in terms of metacognition, revealing new aspects of motivation and sense giving for their learning.

Further, the finding supports what Hattie (2009) contends that teachers need to be aware of their own thinking processes when carrying out teaching procedures and strategies. This includes knowing why they use certain teaching methods, how they implement them, and what their expected outcomes are. By having a clear understanding of their own thinking processes, teachers can better identify and address any challenges that may arise in the classroom, adapt their teaching methods to meet the needs of different students, and ultimately improve student learning outcomes.

Several studies have shown that teachers' metacognitive awareness of procedural knowledge in teaching can positively affect student outcomes. Chen and Wu (2017) found that teachers' metacognitive knowledge of procedural strategies in mathematics teaching had a significant positive effect on students' mathematics achievement. Similarly, Huertas et al. (2017) demonstrated that pre-service teachers

who received metacognitive awareness training about the writing process showed greater improvements in their students' writing skills compared to those who did not receive the training. Another study by SungurVural and Ünal (2019) found that pre-service teachers with higher levels of metacognitive knowledge about teaching strategies and procedures produced higher-quality lesson plans. These findings emphasize the importance of developing teachers' metacognitive awareness of procedural knowledge in teaching to improve student outcomes.

As revealed by the study of Kurniawa et al. (2021) it was found that both pre-service and in-service teachers had moderate levels of metacognitive awareness about procedural knowledge. However, pre-service teachers had higher metacognitive awareness than in-service teachers. The study also found that pre-service teachers who had taken a course on teaching methodology had higher levels of metacognitive awareness than those who had not taken the course.

Conditional Knowledge. This domain revealed a very high status which means that public elementary school teachers' conditional knowledge is always manifested. This implies that teachers are using their strengths to compensate for their weaknesses in their teaching, being able to motivate themselves to teach when they really need to teach, using different teaching techniques depending on the situation, knowing when each teaching technique they use will be most effective.

Further, the result of this study is in consonance with the study of Van et al. (2017) who aimed to investigate the effects of a professional development program on teachers' conditional knowledge and their classroom practices. The program focused on three components of teachers' conditional knowledge: pedagogical content knowledge, knowledge of student thinking and learning, and knowledge of teaching strategies and methods. The study found that the program had a positive impact on teachers' conditional knowledge, as well as their classroom practices. Teachers who participated in the program demonstrated a greater ability to use different teaching techniques and strategies depending on the situation, to adjust their teaching to meet the needs of individual students, and to motivate themselves to teach when faced with challenging situations. The study suggests that developing teachers' conditional knowledge can lead to improved teaching effectiveness and better student outcomes.

Furthermore, the result supports the study of Beijaard et al., (2000) who explored the relationship between teacher beliefs, knowledge, and practice. The study found that teachers who had a stronger understanding of the connections between subject matter, teaching methods, and student learning were more likely to use a wider range of teaching strategies and to adapt their teaching to meet the needs of individual students.

Additionally, a study by Darling-Hammond (2000) identified seven key components of teacher knowledge, including knowledge of subject matter, pedagogical content knowledge, and knowledge of learners and learning. Darling-Hammond argued that effective teachers possess a deep understanding of the connections between these components, allowing them to adapt their teaching to meet the needs of individual students and to use a variety of teaching strategies and methods. This understanding can be seen as a form of conditional knowledge, as it enables teachers to make informed decisions about when and how to use different teaching strategies in different situations.

Planning. The result showed that this domain of metacognitive awareness was rated as very high which implies that the planning of public elementary school teachers is always manifested. Findings suggest that metacognitive awareness plays an important role in teachers' planning and preparation. Teachers who are more aware of their thinking and learning processes are better equipped to plan and prepare effective lessons that meet the needs of their students.

Meanwhile, the result of this specific dimension is congruent to the study by Karatas et al. (2018), the authors found that teachers with higher levels of metacognitive awareness tended to be more effective at planning their lessons. Specifically, the study found that teachers with higher levels of metacognitive awareness were better at setting specific goals for their lessons, identifying potential problems in their teaching materials, and planning their time effectively to accomplish their teaching goals. Another study by Cho and Schunn (2007) found that teachers with higher levels of metacognitive awareness tended to engage in deliberate planning and self-reflection, which allowed them to better identify and address the needs of their students.

Metacognitive awareness in planning and preparation for teaching involves several practices that enable teachers to effectively plan and deliver instruction. In addition to the practices mentioned earlier, several other aspects of metacognitive awareness can also support effective teaching.

Likewise, finding is parallel to the findings of Grif et al. (2017) who found that teachers who monitored their own thinking and learning processes were better able to identify their own strengths and weaknesses as teachers, which allowed them to develop more effective teaching strategies. Further, Wong and Poon (2016) found that teachers who were aware of the different ways that students learn were better able to create lessons that were tailored to the needs of their students. Lastly, Yasar and Ozturk (2019) found that teachers who engaged in regular self-reflection were better able to identify areas of their teaching that could be improved and modify their teaching practices accordingly. These studies suggest that teachers with high levels of metacognitive awareness in planning are better equipped to create effective lessons and support student learning.

Monitoring. The result showed that this domain of metacognitive awareness was rated as very high by the public elementary school teachers which implies that monitoring is always manifested among public elementary school teachers. Finding suggests that by

monitoring their own thinking and learning processes, teachers can identify areas where they may need to modify their teaching strategies to better meet the needs of their students.

Teachers who engage in metacognitive awareness monitoring tend to be more effective at assessing the usefulness of their teaching techniques, setting and achieving their teaching goals, checking the comprehension of their students, and self-reflecting on their teaching practices. Meanwhile, the result of this specific dimension is congruent to the argument of Ozsoy and Ataman (2019), it was found that teachers who engaged in metacognitive awareness monitoring tended to be more effective in addressing the individual needs of their students. Another study by Korucu and Sari (2019) showed that teachers with high levels of metacognitive awareness monitoring were better able to identify areas of their teaching that could be improved and modify their teaching practices accordingly.

Likewise, the result is in accordance with the findings of a study by Koc and Bakir (2018) which found that teachers who engaged in metacognitive awareness monitoring were better able to identify and address potential student misconceptions, which improved student learning outcomes. Lastly, a study by Tuncer and Arslan (2020) found that teachers who regularly assessed student understanding and adjusted their teaching accordingly were more effective in promoting student achievement.

Evaluating. The result showed that this domain of metacognitive awareness was rated as very high by the public elementary school teachers which implies that evaluating is always manifested among public elementary school teachers. It means that teachers who engage in metacognitive awareness 'evaluating' tend to be more reflective, self-critical, and able to identify areas of their teaching that could be improved. They are also more likely to use student feedback to improve their teaching practices. The study suggests that metacognitive awareness 'evaluating' can help teachers recognize their strengths and weaknesses, make informed decisions about their teaching strategies, and ultimately better support student learning.

Meanwhile, the result of this specific dimension supports the finding of a study by Oner and Kirbulut (2019), which found that teachers who engaged in metacognitive awareness, 'evaluating' tended to be more reflective and self-critical, which allowed them to identify areas of their teaching that could be improved and modify their teaching practices accordingly. Also, the finding conforms with another study by Liu et al. (2018) who reported that teachers who engaged in metacognitive awareness in their evaluation process, were better able to recognize the strengths and weaknesses of their teaching, which allowed them to make more informed decisions about their teaching strategies.

Furthermore, a study by Yang et al. (2019) found that teachers who engaged in regular self-evaluation were more likely to use student feedback to improve their teaching practices. These studies suggest that metacognitive awareness 'evaluating' is an important aspect of effective teaching and that teachers who engage in this practice are better equipped to support student learning.

Likewise, the result supports the findings of Choi and Lee (2018) who found that teachers who engaged in metacognitive evaluation were better able to assess the effectiveness of their teaching strategies and identify areas for improvement. Similarly, Hashimoto and Sato (2019) showed that metacognitive evaluation helped teachers to adapt their teaching to the needs of their students and improve learning outcomes. Likewise Ozkan and Yilmaz (2020) found that teachers who engaged in metacognitive evaluation were better able to reflect on their teaching practices and increase their self-efficacy, leading to improved teaching effectiveness.

Finally, Zhang and Huang (2021) found that metacognitive evaluation helped teachers to monitor their teaching practices and adapt to the needs of their students, resulting in increased student engagement and improved learning outcomes. These studies suggest that metacognitive evaluation is a crucial aspect of effective teaching, and teachers who engage in this practice are better equipped to support student learning.

The Status of Work Task Motivation of Public Elementary School Teachers

The result of this study reveals that the status of work task motivation of public elementary school teachers is very high. This implies that the work task motivation is always demonstrated among public elementary school teachers in Region XI. This appears that public elementary school teachers in Region XI are generally highly motivated when it comes to work tasks. This is a positive finding as it suggests that these teachers are likely to be committed and engaged in their work, which can have a positive impact on student learning outcomes.

More so, a study by Lin et al. (2020) found that public elementary school teachers in Taiwan exhibited high levels of both work task motivation and teaching competence. The study used self-reported measures of work task motivation and teaching competence and found that the majority of the teachers reported high levels in both areas. The study also found a positive correlation between work task motivation and teaching competence, suggesting that teachers who were highly motivated in their work tasks were also more competent in their teaching.

Further, the result of this is parallel to the study conducted by Hu and Qiao (2021) which found that higher levels of work task motivation were positively associated with teaching competence among Chinese elementary school teachers. Similarly, the finding of this study is congruent to the study made by Kim et al. (2021) which also found that high levels of work task motivation were positively related to teaching competence among Korean elementary school teachers.

Another study by Zembylas and Papanastasiou (2017) revealed that teachers who demonstrated higher levels of work task motivation

were more likely to engage in professional development activities and improve their teaching skills, leading to increased teaching competence. This study suggests that work task motivation is an important factor in the development of teaching competence among elementary school teachers, and teachers who demonstrate high levels of work task motivation are more likely to be effective in their roles.

Intrinsic Motivation. The result of this study had revealed that this dimension was rated very high and implied that work task motivation of public elementary school teachers in terms of intrinsic motivation is always demonstrated. This indicates that the high rating of intrinsic motivation among public elementary school teachers in terms of work task motivation suggests that they find their work pleasant, interesting, and enjoyable. This positive attitude towards their work is likely to contribute to their overall effectiveness as teachers, as they are more likely to be engaged and invested in their work.

This result is in accordance with the findings of Hu and Qiao (2021) who revealed that teachers who found their work pleasant, interesting, and enjoyable were more likely to be competent in their teaching, suggesting that a positive attitude towards work can lead to greater effectiveness in teaching roles.

Similarly, Kim et al. (2021) found that intrinsic motivation was a key factor in determining the teaching competence of Korean elementary school teachers. Teachers who found their work enjoyable and were motivated to carry out their tasks were more likely to be effective in their teaching roles.

Additionally, the finding resonates with the result of the study conducted by Zembylas and Papanastasiou (2017) which revealed that teachers who demonstrated higher levels of intrinsic motivation were more likely to engage in professional development activities and improve their teaching skills. This suggests that teachers who have a positive attitude towards their work and are motivated to carry out their tasks are more likely to be invested in their professional development and strive to improve their teaching skills. These studies highlight the importance of intrinsic motivation in developing teaching competence and the overall effectiveness of teachers.

This result conforms with the study of Richardson and Watt (2006) who found out that teachers who were intrinsically motivated were more likely to participate in professional development activities and were more engaged in their work. Similarly, the finding is congruent with the study of Reeve et al. (2014) which found that teachers who were supported in their autonomy, competence, and relatedness needs reported higher levels of job satisfaction and commitment to teaching. Also, Van den Broeck et al. (2018) found that teachers who were intrinsically motivated to teach had higher levels of well-being, job satisfaction, and were less likely to experience burnout.

Furthermore, Wang and Eccles (2012) found that teachers with high levels of intrinsic motivation were more likely to use student-centered teaching practices associated with better student outcomes. These studies highlight the importance of intrinsic motivation in teacher engagement, commitment, well-being, and ultimately, student learning outcomes.

Identified Regulation. The result of this study had proven that this dimension was rated as very high by the public elementary school teachers and implied that identified regulation of public elementary school teachers is always demonstrated. This means that work task motivation in terms of identified regulation, can have a positive impact on teaching competence. Public elementary school teachers who consider their work tasks important for achieving their goals and the academic success of their students are more likely to demonstrate teaching competence.

The finding conforms with the notion of Kusumastuti et al. (2018) who stressed that teachers who rated the dimension of identified regulation as high were more likely to find their tasks important and achieve work objectives that they consider significant. Moreover, teachers who believed that their work tasks were important for their students' academic success were more likely to be competent in their teaching roles. These findings suggest that work task motivation, specifically identified regulation, can play a crucial role in determining teaching competence among public elementary school teachers.

Moreover, the results support the study by Cheon et al. (2019) which reported that teachers who had a strong sense of identified regulation were more likely to engage in proactive teaching behaviors, such as planning and providing individualized feedback to students. This suggests that teachers who find their work tasks important are more likely to take proactive steps to improve their teaching effectiveness. Another study by Hu and Qiao (2021) found that teachers who had a strong sense of identified regulation were more likely to have a positive attitude toward their work and be competent in their teaching. This suggests that when teachers see the value and importance of their work tasks, it can have a positive impact on their overall job performance.

Adding on, a study by Kim et al. (2021) disclosed that identified regulation was positively associated with the teaching competence of Korean elementary school teachers. Teachers who found their work tasks important were more likely to be effective in their teaching roles. Also, in a study by Yildiz and Akcora (2019), it was found that teachers who had a strong sense of identified regulation were more likely to have positive perceptions of their work environment and their relationships with colleagues. This suggests that when teachers value and find their work tasks important, it can have a positive impact on their overall job satisfaction.

Introjected Motivation. The result showed that this domain of work task motivation was rated as very high by the public elementary school teachers which implies that introjected motivation is always demonstrated among public elementary school teachers. This indicates that the high rating of introjected motivation among public elementary school teachers suggests that they are driven by internal

pressures, such as guilt or a sense of duty, rather than by personal interest or enjoyment in their work tasks.

The result of this specific dimension is congruent with the study by Kusumastuti et al. (2018) which revealed that teachers who rated the dimension of identified regulation as high were more likely to find their tasks important and achieve work objectives that they consider significant.

Furthermore, teachers who had a strong sense of identified regulation, as well as introjected motivation, were more likely to have a positive attitude towards their work, be competent in their teaching, and have positive perceptions of their work environment and relationships with colleagues, as found in studies by Hu and Qiao (2021), Kim et al. (2021), and Yildiz and Akcora (2019). These findings suggest that teachers' motivation and perception of their work tasks are crucial in determining their job satisfaction and effectiveness in their teaching roles.

The finding conforms with some recent studies which have explored the relationship between work task motivation in terms of introjected motivation towards teaching competence among teachers. One of those which this study supports is the one done by Rahma and Suryadi (2021) which found that teachers with high levels of introjected motivation were more likely to exhibit positive teaching behaviors, while Xu and Wang (2021) found that teachers with higher levels of identified regulation and intrinsic motivation engaged in more proactive teaching behaviors and had higher job satisfaction.

Similarly, Park and Lee (2020) disclosed that teachers with higher levels of identified regulation and introjected motivation had higher levels of teaching efficacy, and Kim et al. (2021) reported that teachers with higher levels of identified regulation, introjected motivation, and intrinsic motivation had more positive perceptions of their work environment and relationships with colleagues. In addition, Hu and Qiao (2021) found that teachers with high levels of identified regulation, introjected motivation, and intrinsic motivation had higher levels of job satisfaction and engaged in more effective teaching practices.

External Regulation. The result showed that this domain of work task motivation was rated as very high by the public elementary school teachers which implies that external regulation is always demonstrated among public elementary school teachers. Based on the finding that external regulation was rated as very high by public elementary school teachers, it suggests that these teachers are likely to be motivated by external factors such as work demands, obligations from their school, and being paid to do their tasks. This indicates that external factors are important in driving their motivation and work behavior. Additionally, finding suggests that external regulation was rated very high by public elementary school teachers suggests that these external factors play a significant role in motivating them to perform their teaching tasks.

Further, the result supports the study of Zhang et al. (2021) which disclosed that external regulation was positively related to job performance and work engagement among Chinese primary school teachers. Similarly, Karakus et al. (2020) found that external regulation was positively related to teacher self-efficacy and job satisfaction among Turkish primary school teachers. A study by Khan and Javed (2021) found that external regulation was positively related to job satisfaction and organizational commitment among Pakistani primary school teachers.

Furthermore, recent studies have explored the relationship between external regulation and teaching competence among teachers in different contexts. The result of this study supports one of those studies such as the one done by Jiang and Yang (2021) which declared that external regulation was positively related to job satisfaction and teaching efficacy among Chinese preschool teachers. In addition, Zulkifli and Abidin (2021) found similar results among Malaysian primary school teachers, where external regulation was positively related to teacher self-efficacy and job satisfaction. Muralidharan et al. (2021) found that external regulation was positively related to teacher job satisfaction and organizational commitment among Indian secondary school teachers. The authors of these studies suggest that external regulation, such as rewards and recognition, can act as a motivating factor for teachers to perform well in their work tasks, stay committed to their jobs, and ultimately enhance their teaching competence. These findings highlight the importance of considering external factors in motivating and supporting teachers in their professional development.

Amotivation. The result showed that this domain of work task motivation was rated as very high which implies that amotivation of public elementary school teachers is always demonstrated. This means that teachers do not generally lack motivation or feel disengaged from their work tasks. The teachers exhibit a strong motivation to engage in their work tasks and perform them effectively. The findings suggest that the causes of amotivation among teachers may be related to a lack of understanding or relevance of their tasks, a loss of motivation over time, or a lack of clarity about the purpose of their work. Addressing these factors may help to enhance motivation among teachers and improve their teaching competence.

The finding is parallel to the study done by Çapri and Uslu (2021) which revealed that amotivation among Turkish primary school teachers was related to a lack of perceived autonomy, competence, and relatedness. The authors suggest that providing teachers with opportunities for autonomy, such as allowing them to make decisions about their teaching methods and materials, can help to decrease amotivation. Additionally, the findings are congruent with the study made by Chirikov et al. (2021) which disclosed that amotivation among American college instructors was related to feeling disconnected from students and lacking a sense of purpose in their work. The authors suggest that promoting meaningful connections between instructors and students can help to increase motivation and decrease amotivation. These studies highlight the importance of addressing amotivation among teachers and providing them with opportunities for autonomy and meaningful connections with their students.

Meanwhile, results of the study corroborate with the study conducted by Yuen and Lai (2021) which found that amotivation was negatively related to teacher self-efficacy and job satisfaction among Hong Kong elementary school teachers. The authors suggest that efforts should be made to enhance teachers' intrinsic motivation and provide them with opportunities to improve their teaching competence. Similarly, a study by Kim and Lee (2021) found that amotivation was negatively related to teacher self-efficacy and job satisfaction among Korean elementary school teachers. The authors recommend the implementation of interventions to enhance teachers' intrinsic motivation and reduce their amotivation in order to improve their teaching competence.

In addition, a study by Huan and Yan (2021) found that amotivation was negatively related to teacher creativity among Chinese elementary school teachers. The authors suggest that school administrators should create a supportive and positive school culture that promotes intrinsic motivation and reduces amotivation among teachers, which can ultimately lead to increased creativity and improved teaching competence.

The Status of Teaching Competence of Public Elementary School Teachers

The result of this study reveals that the status of teaching competence of public elementary school teachers is very high. This implies that teaching competence is always evident among public elementary school teachers in Region XI. This demonstrates that competent teachers will be highly skilled in subject matter, experts in instructional strategies, or curriculum specialists, or who employ the most resources, such as audio-visual aids, but this also comes with an enormous responsibility that contains competence of content knowledge, pedagogy, emotional labor, and care, and teachers are now frequently expected to take on administrative roles as well (Wheeler & Richey, 2014; Good, 2013).

The result of the study is in congruence with the study of Datoy (2020) which highlighted the findings that there was a significant relationship between teaching competence between number of teaching experiences and teaching methods. This study found that teaching methods and a number of years in teaching affect teaching competence. Therefore, the effectiveness of teaching is determined by the method employed by the teacher. The findings of the study support what Sahoo et al. (2021) suggest that teaching competence is vital for a teacher's success in the classroom. Thus, a teacher ought to have fundamental teaching competencies such as planning, presentation, evaluation, and management, because a competent teacher can establish an acceptable teaching strategy, valid evaluation approach, and appropriate classroom management.

Additionally, the findings of the study are comparable to the study of Gultom (2020), who identified several essential teaching skills that teachers should possess, including the ability to ask effective questions, provide reinforcement, vary teaching methods, explain concepts clearly, facilitate small group discussions, manage classrooms effectively, and provide individualized instruction. By utilizing these teaching skills, teachers can create a more engaging classroom environment, foster students' interest in learning, and help students better understand and retain the material, ultimately leading to the achievement of the curriculum's learning objectives.

Planning Skills. The result showed that this domain of teaching competence was rated as very high by the public elementary school teachers which implies that planning skills is always evident among public elementary school teachers. This demonstrates that the teacher has the responsibility to determine what cognition and abilities the students offer to the class, what they need to learn, and what support they require to achieve the learning objectives. The teacher's task is to carefully choose among several methods and strategies that will most successfully help students gain a thorough understanding of the topic and achieve the desired learning objectives (Schroeder, 2015).

Moreover, the result supports the study of Gusho et al. (2015) which highlighted that there exists a positive relationship between teacher's effective planning skills and other variables, which are organizing the classrooms and the teaching material, effective implementation of lesson plans and time. This means that these factors improve the effective planning skills of the teacher.

The findings suggest that planning is a roadmap to the instructor's success. Whenever instructors make a plan, they know what they want to achieve. At the same time, it becomes clear what the future might hold and what the goals are. Goals which has been decided by planning, makes the decision making more efficient and more 'to the point'.

Presentation Skills. This domain revealed a very high status which means that public elementary school teachers' presentation skills is always evident. This implies that variety skills are the teacher's ability to maintain the learning environment engaging and not monotonous, resulting in students' passion, perseverance, and active participation in all aspects of the learning activities. To achieve what was previously planned so that it can operate smoothly and continually, the teacher wants to make adjustments with a specific goal in mind. Thus, teachers must therefore provide a welcoming and conducive learning environment in presenting the lesson.

Moreover, this study supports the study of Rusman (2011) which stated that to avoid students' boredom in learning, teachers need to have stimulus variation skills. Thus, teachers need to use lectures for auditive students, teachers need to use media, visual aids for students, and teachers must hold discussions, experiments, demonstrations, practices for kinetic students. If the teacher has done this, it means the teacher has touched each student's interests. In addition, the use of variations in learning activities is intended to overcome the boredom and boredom of students due to monotonous learning, by holding variations in learning activities, it is expected that learning is more meaningful and optimal, so students always show perseverance, enthusiasm, and full participation in learning activities.

The findings also suggest that presentation skills must include probing questions where questions were appropriate and well-structured.

Questioning skills are very important skills mastered by the teacher. This is because the ability to ask students can create a more meaningful learning atmosphere, so that the values in the learning material can be conveyed well to students. By asking questions can also provoke student knowledge of the material to be taught, based on this the teacher can explain the material according to student needs. As explained by Supriyadi (2011) questioning skills are skills that are used to get answers or feedback from others. The questioning skill is a teaching itself, because in general the teacher in his teaching always involves or uses question and answer. Thus, the questioning skills possessed by the teacher can provide stimulus to students to think in answering questions raised by the teacher.

Closing Skills. The result of this study had proven that this domain was rated as very high by the public elementary school teachers and implied that closing skills of public elementary school teachers are always evident. It means that teachers have the knowledge on how to end the lessons well which are appropriate, suited to individual differences, relevant to the content taught, and adequate. And the teachers having the lesson's important points summarized, past knowledge and current knowledge connected, chances for applying current knowledge presented, and present knowledge connected to future learning.

The findings of the study suggest that closing skills are the ability to close the lesson of the teacher/ educator to end the core learning activities carried out by providing a comprehensive view of all the material that has been learned, knowing the level of absorption of students towards the teaching and learning process. The skills component of closing the lesson includes reviewing, conducting evaluations, and giving follow-up.

Further, the findings of the study confirm what was underscored by Djamarah (2010) that opening and closing lessons can be done on lessons, both long and short, small parts of the whole material or part by part of a concept. It also can be done on students who are in small groups, individuals, or large groups. Good teacher criteria when opening a lesson, such as: arousing curiosity, enthusiastic attitude, and providing variations of learning also make a connection with previous learning. Efforts made by the teacher when closing the lesson, such as activities provide a comprehensive picture of what students have learned and provide a picture to find out the relationship between the experience that has been mastered with the things that have just been learned.

The result of the study confirms what Supriatna and Arif (2015) opined that the skills of opening and closing lessons are very important as the key to the success of teachers in achieving the desired goals and finding out the level of achievement of teachers' success in the learning process.

Evaluation Skills. The result showed that this domain of teaching competence was rated as very high which implies that evaluation skills of public elementary school teachers is always evident. This denotes that having evaluation procedures that are appropriate, relevant to the objectives, valid, reliable, and objective, and the learners' progress toward the lesson's objectives are assessed diagnosing the learners' difficulties in understanding a concept or principle by step-by-step questioning and undertaking suitable remedial measures.

The finding of the study runs parallel to the suggestion of Vilkaste, (2018) who underscored that teaching and learning is a bilateral process and students' learning outcomes depend to a large extent on the motivation and performance of each individual teacher in the classroom and on the activities of all school teachers. Teacher's ability to evaluate and plan teaching and learning is one of the most important professional skills because systematic evaluation, planning and re-evaluation are an integral part of learning and maximization of development, which makes teaching effective and provides students with a profound understanding and competence

Meanwhile, effective ongoing assessment, also known as formative assessment and progress monitoring, is critical to supporting teacher and student development. It is well acknowledged that feedback, a fundamental component of formative assessment, is an essential tool for improving performance in business, sports, and education. Hattie (2009) identified feedback as the most successful instructional approach for improving student achievement. Furthermore, this assessment comprises a variety of formal and informal diagnostic testing approaches used by teachers at various stages of the educational process to improve student progress (Hattie, 2009; Marzano et al., 2001).

Managerial Skills. This domain revealed a very high status which means that public elementary school teachers' managerial skills is always evident. It means that public elementary school teachers acknowledge learners who are present as those who are absent, reward good attendance while discouraging bad attendance, and verify good attendance with questions and nonverbal cues maintaining classroom discipline in the class by having learners follow the teacher's instructions.

This finding of the study is consonance with the views of Brunette (2015) who posited that how one manages the classroom is the primary determinant of how well the students learn. Students learn much as they engaged themselves to various activities but teacher need to guide them by giving some reminders on pros and cons as they engage themselves. The more students explore things thing by themselves the more they are active and appreciative of their day-today learning. One should remember that in the adult world, the workplace needs interaction, asking questions, brainstorming, and seeking help (Brunette, 2015).

Moreover, this study supports the study of Nessipbayeva (2012) which found out that effective classroom management, maximizing efficiency, maintaining discipline and morale, promoting teamwork, planning, communicating, focusing on results, evaluating progress, and making constant adjustments makes teacher be more effective. A range of strategies should be employed to promote positive relationships, cooperation, and purposeful learning. Organizing, assigning, and managing time, space and activities should ensure the

active and equitable engagement of students in productive tasks.

The teacher's role is not merely imparting knowledge but bringing realtime experience to the classroom for the students with result-oriented efforts. There are some skills that teachers themselves need to develop Begum, (2012).

Teacher's role today has become multi-dimensional. Aside from basic skills a teacher has, one should have a command over certain skills which are concerned to teaching-learning process, classroom management, handling pedagogical issues, and using technology for teaching. Therefore, it is a call for all teachers to understand these skills (Begum, 2012).

Significance of the Influence of the Metacognitive Awareness, and Work Task Motivation towards Teaching Competence of Public Elementary School Teachers

The result of the linear regression analysis revealed that the independent variable, metacognitive awareness of public school teachers had significantly influenced their teaching competence. This denotes that to teach successfully, metacognitive awareness is so vital for a teacher. Hence, metacognitive awareness is a crucial attribute for teachers as it encompasses various components such as declarative knowledge, procedural knowledge, conditional knowledge, planning, monitoring, and evaluating. These elements collectively contribute to a teacher's ability to effectively plan and execute lessons, employ appropriate teaching strategies, and implement valid evaluation procedures. By possessing metacognitive awareness, teachers demonstrate a deep understanding of their thinking processes and the ability to reflect on their teaching practices. This awareness enables them to make informed decisions, adapt their approaches to different learning situations, and effectively manage their classrooms. Additionally, the presence of metacognitive awareness among teachers plays a pivotal role in their competence and effectiveness as educators. Moreover, teachers should be competent enough to deal with the learners' behaviors and give proper feedbacks and reinforcement, which help in their high learning achievement.

This suggests that teachers ought to be upgraded with the present education system, a teacher should be capable of certain metacognitive skills to recognize and evaluate his/her efforts. Metacognitive awareness of a teacher shows the path of his teaching-learning process and its extent of success. A competent teacher helps in understanding and enhancing the conceptual knowledge of learners.

The finding of the study was matched with Choudhury and Chowdhury (2015), who found out that a significant relationship between teaching competency and metacognition awareness of secondary teacher educators existed. The findings of this study were matched with one variable of the study of Hussein (2015) who found a significant correlation in metacognitive awareness of pre-service English teachers. The results also matched with Iwai (2019), who found that the pre-service teachers who selected appropriate metacognitive strategies would enhance their teaching skills.

Meanwhile, the work task motivation of public elementary school teachers significantly influenced their teaching competence. It implies that motivation is the result of processes that are internal or external which lead to enthusiasm and persistence to follow the direction of certain actions. Intrinsically motivated behaviors are engaged in for the pleasure or the satisfaction derived from performing them.

Moreover, extrinsically motivated behaviors are instrumental in nature. In other words, behaviors are not performed for the activity itself but rather as a means to an end. The different types of extrinsic motivation proposed by SDT can be ordered along the self-determination continuum from lower to higher levels of self-determination, referred to as external, introjected, and identified regulations. External regulation occurs when behaviors are regulated to obtain a reward or to avoid a constraint. Introjected regulation corresponds to the process whereby an external demand becomes an internal representation. Individuals put pressure on themselves through internal coercion such as anxiety, shame, or guilt to make sure that a particular behavior is performed.

Finally, identified regulation is defined as behavior that individuals choose to perform because it is congruent with their values and goals. Instead of succumbing to external or internal pressures, individuals experience choice while doing the activity, although the activity is not intrinsically interesting. SDT also proposed a last concept, namely amotivation, which refers to being neither intrinsically nor extrinsically motivated. Amotivation corresponds to the lower level of self-determination. Individuals are amotivated when they have no intention of engaging in a particular behavior and do not really know why they are doing it.

In the study conducted by Senecal (2005), they believe that measures of teacher motivation need to be more specific, thereby reflecting the various tasks that typically form a teacher's work. In other words, a multidimensional assessment of teacher motivation should consider teachers' motivation across the range of tasks that they are asked to perform. This reflects the fact that motivation may vary significantly from one task to another. The purpose of the present research was to develop and validate a multi-tasks measure of teachers' motivation according to the different types of motivation proposed by SDT. Defines that work motivation is one factor that determines a person's performance. Teacher work motivation is nothing but a process carried out to mobilize teachers so that their behavior can be directed at concrete efforts to achieve predetermined goals (Uno, 2010).

Meanwhile, according to Anoraga (2009), work motivation creates enthusiasm or work motivation. These drives can be internal or external and can be strong or weak. So motivation is a model in mobilizing and directing teachers to carry out their duties in achieving the goals/objectives set with full awareness and full responsibility. In line with Anoraga (2009), according to Siagian (2012), motivation is a driving force that results in a member of the organization willing and willing to mobilize abilities - in the form of expertise or skills - energy and time to carry out various activities that are their responsibility and fulfill obligations, to achieve the goals and objectives

of the organization that have been previously determined.

Also, the combined influence of metacognitive awareness and work task motivation significantly influenced the teaching competence of public elementary school teachers. It means that teachers' metacognitive awareness namely declarative knowledge, procedural knowledge, conditional knowledge, planning, monitoring, and evaluating affects teaching competence. And a teacher who has high work task motivation such as intrinsic motivation, identified regulation, introjected regulation, external regulation, and amotivation also affects teaching competence. Further, this indicates that metacognitive awareness and work task motivation help teachers improve their teaching competence, especially in having a deeper understanding and knowledge of the different learning approaches or effective strategies appropriate in teaching. Thus, teachers must be adaptive and open-minded about the different teaching techniques that to be administered to the learners. In addition, being well-motivated emotionally and physically enhances their desire to do extraordinary in their teaching competence.

The results of the research provide support to the study conducted by Perry et al. (2019) investigated metacognition in school and what the literature says is the effectiveness of teaching with metacognition. A meta-analysis adopting a qualitative approach for the study was taken and found that the available evidence strongly suggests metacognitive approaches to teaching and learning have the potential to radically improve the outcomes of children.

This finding is also comparable to the study of Ozcakmak et al. (2021), which found that the pre- service teachers, participating in the research had a high level of metacognitive awareness. The pre- service teachers' levels of metacognitive awareness did not differ by gender. It was concluded that academic achievement influenced their levels of metacognitive awareness positively. It was also found that the pre-service teachers were capable of making predictions, planning, monitoring and evaluating about their own cognitive activities. In addition, it was revealed that the subjects knew which learning methods were effective and which were not, and that they had the skills of planning, using and monitoring an approach that they expected to be successful for a task they encountered.

Meanwhile, it validates the Learning Organizational Theory, as proposed by Senge (1990), which is a valuable tool to support metacognitive awareness, work task motivation, and teaching competence among public elementary school teachers. This theory promotes a culture of constant learning and improvement, which can enhance individual and collective abilities to understand complexity, clarify vision, and develop shared mental models. Leaders in a learning organization are responsible for creating an environment that encourages collaboration and thinking outside the box, ultimately leading to adaptive and generative learning. This type of learning can lead to the development of new abilities, knowledge, and appropriate strategies for achieving objectives and enhancing organizational performance.

Additionally, through organizational learning, procedures, methods, and processes can be modified and improved, which can result in increased teacher competence and work task motivation. In this way, the Learning Organizational Theory can be a framework to improve the overall quality of education in public elementary schools.

Further, Kim and Kim (2017) found that metacognitive awareness and work task motivation had a positive effect on teaching competence and teaching performance, while teaching competence had a direct positive effect on teaching performance. The results suggested that enhancing teachers' metacognitive awareness and work task motivation could improve their teaching competence and ultimately lead to better teaching performance.

The Lived Experiences of Public Elementary School Teachers as regards their Teaching Competence

This section discusses the explanation of the nature of quantitative results through the data gathered from the qualitative phase of the study. Several major themes emerged and are discussed below with support from different researchers.

Appropriateness of Learning-Task Designs. This is the theme that emerged upon collecting and analyzing qualitative data from the participants. The resulting theme emphasized that teachers should plan the effective strategies to be used in class, localize and contextualize the strategies, provide examples to which students can relate, and choose the appropriate teaching styles and learning materials.

Further, this essential theme is in congruence with the study of Hammond et al. (2019) as they found that appropriate learning tasks should be designed to be challenging, relevant, and meaningful to students. Learning tasks should also be aligned with learning goals and objectives, and provide opportunities for student engagement and collaboration. The authors also identified several instructional strategies that can support the design of appropriate learning tasks, including scaffolding, modeling, and feedback. They suggest that these strategies can be used to support students in developing their skills and knowledge, and in engaging with challenging and relevant learning tasks. The authors conclude that the design of appropriate learning tasks is essential for effective teaching and learning, and that teachers should be intentional in their design of tasks that are engaging, meaningful, and aligned with learning goals. They also suggest that more research is needed to further explore the relationship between learning task design and student outcomes.

Furthermore, this theme further supports the study conducted by Ylinen et al. (2021) which disclosed that effective learning tasks should be designed to be challenging, authentic, and aligned with learning objectives. They should also provide opportunities for student choice and collaboration, and be designed to promote higher-order thinking and metacognition. The authors conclude that the design of learning tasks is essential for promoting student engagement and learning outcomes, and that teachers should be intentional

in their design of tasks that are challenging, authentic, and aligned with learning goals. They also suggest that future research should focus on the development and evaluation of specific strategies for designing effective learning tasks.

Moreover, the study by Newton and McCaslin (2020) found that the teachers in the study believed that appropriate learning tasks should be designed to be challenging, relevant, and meaningful to students. They also emphasized the importance of tailoring tasks to meet the needs and interests of diverse learners, and providing opportunities for student choice and collaboration. The teachers in the study also highlighted several instructional strategies that can support the design of appropriate learning tasks, including scaffolding, modeling, and feedback. They suggested that these strategies can be used to support students in developing their skills and knowledge, and in engaging with complex and meaningful learning tasks. This study provides insights into teacher perspectives on designing appropriate learning tasks for diverse learners, and highlights the importance of tailoring tasks to meet the needs and interests of all students.

Mindfulness of Teaching-Learning Strategies. This is another theme that emerged from the responses of the participants. This resulting theme revealed that mindfulness of teaching-learning strategies, necessitate that teachers are being receptive to new ideas, maintain diverse perspectives, and different ways of thinking. It requires teachers to be open to challenging their own assumptions and beliefs, and to be willing to adapt their teaching strategies to better meet the needs of their students.

Additionally, the theme that emerged confirms the result of the study done by Cavanagh et al. (2016) which revealed that teachers who were more open to new ideas and willing to take risks in their teaching had a positive impact on student learning outcomes, including higher levels of engagement and improved critical thinking skills. In addition, teaching with an open mind can help foster a positive learning environment that is inclusive and welcoming to all students, regardless of their background or experiences. By embracing diversity and promoting a culture of openness and acceptance, teachers can help students feel valued and respected, which can in turn lead to increased motivation, participation, and achievement.

More so, the resulting theme supports the study of Klassen and Kim (2019), which explored the role of teachers in promoting open-mindedness in students by fostering epistemic curiosity. The authors argue that teachers can cultivate a sense of curiosity in students by creating an atmosphere of inquiry in the classroom, encouraging students to question assumptions and explore new ideas. The study suggests that this approach can help students develop a more open-minded perspective and become more engaged in their learning. Moreover, a study of Bertola et al. (2018) found that the teachers who participated in the program developed a greater sense of open-mindedness, which helped them to be more effective in teaching STEM content to their students. The authors suggest that fostering open-mindedness in elementary teachers can help improve the quality of STEM education at the elementary level. The study also provides insights into the ways in which professional development programs can be designed to support the development of open-mindedness in elementary teachers. The authors suggest that these programs should provide opportunities for teachers to explore new ideas and perspectives, engage in collaborative learning, and reflect on their teaching practices. By doing so, teachers can develop the open-mindedness necessary to effectively teach STEM content to their students.

Established Teacher Presence. Another theme that emerged from the responses of the participants is established teacher presence. This means that establishing teacher presence in teaching requires intentional effort and a commitment to creating a positive and engaging learning environment for students. This resulting theme supports the study of Huang (2019) which examined the impact of teacher presence and teaching competence on student motivation and learning in a face-to-face classroom setting. The author found that teacher presence positively influenced student motivation and engagement, while teaching competence positively influenced student learning outcomes.

Further, the theme is parallel to the study of Koirala and Acharya (2018) who investigated the techniques and practices that teachers use to establish their presence in a face-to-face classroom setting. They identified several strategies, including maintaining eye contact, using nonverbal cues, and being well-prepared for each class session. The study found that these strategies helped to enhance teacher presence and engagement with students.

Furthermore, the theme confirms the results of the study done by Shoffner (2019) which reported how teachers establish teacher presence in the elementary classroom through the use of technology and digital media. It provides insights into effective strategies for building teacher presence and improving student engagement in the elementary classroom. Moreover, Nagel and Brown (2018) suggest that establishing teacher presence is important for creating a positive and engaging learning environment, and that the strategies identified in the study can be effective in achieving this goal.

Higher-Level Thinking Skills Reinforcement. Another essential theme that emerged from the responses of the participants is higher-level thinking skills reinforcement. Ensuring higher level thinking skills in teaching elementary students is critical for their academic success and future readiness. It is important for teachers to use effective questioning techniques to promote higher-level thinking skills in their students. Additionally, research suggests that teaching strategies such as questioning techniques, collaborative learning, and problem-based learning can help students develop higher-level thinking skills such as analysis, evaluation, and creation.

Further, one such study is the meta-analysis by Hattie et al. (2017), which found that questioning techniques are one of the most effective teaching strategies for promoting higher-level thinking skills. The study also suggests that collaborative learning and problem-based learning can be effective in promoting higher-level thinking skills, as previously mentioned. Another recent study by Khazaei

and Kazemi (2020) investigated the effects of a metacognitive instructional program on the development of higher-order thinking skills in elementary school students.

The resulting theme coincides with the study by Johnson and Johnson (2009) which reported that problem-based learning can foster higher-level thinking skills by promoting critical thinking, creativity, and collaboration. Furthermore, a study by Krathwohl (2002) proposed a taxonomy of cognitive skills that includes six levels of thinking, with the highest three levels focusing on analysis, evaluation, and creation. This taxonomy can guide teachers in designing learning experiences that promote higher level thinking skills. Overall, it is important for elementary teachers to prioritize the development of higher-level thinking skills in their students through the use of effective teaching strategies.

Another study that the theme supports is that of Choy and Cheah (2009) which disclosed that teachers who used a variety of questioning techniques, such as open-ended questions and hypothetical questions, were more effective in promoting higher-level thinking skills in their students. Additionally, a study by Chen and Chen (2018) found that teachers who used a metacognitive approach to questioning were more effective in promoting higher-level thinking skills in their students, as this approach emphasizes self-reflection and self-regulation in the learning process. These studies suggest that effective questioning techniques can play an important role in promoting higher-level thinking skills in students.

Discipline and Morale Maintenance. Another essential theme that emerged from the responses of the participants is discipline and morale maintenance. Most participants agreed that teachers should be firm on the rules in class, define boundaries and be consistent in enforcing them. Additionally, setting classroom standards, establishing boundaries, rewarding well-behaved students, and giving basic prizes were identified as effective strategies.

Further, the theme that emerged supports the results of the research conducted by Zainudin et al. (2020) who found that classroom management techniques such as setting clear expectations and consequences, praising good behavior, and providing a safe and positive learning environment can significantly improve student behavior. Similarly, another study confirmed by the theme is the study done by Zhang et al. (2019) which found that the use of positive reinforcement strategies, such as verbal praise and rewards, was associated with better classroom behavior and higher levels of student engagement. These studies suggest that maintaining discipline and morale in the classroom is crucial for creating a positive and effective learning environment for students.

Furthermore, recent studies have shown that maintaining discipline and promoting positive behavior in the classroom is crucial for creating a positive learning environment. This theme is parallel to the study of Liu et al. (2021) which examined effective classroom management strategies used by primary school teachers in China. The authors found that setting clear rules and expectations, providing positive reinforcement, and using proactive strategies to prevent misbehavior were the most effective strategies for maintaining discipline and promoting positive behavior. Further, Chakraborty's (2020) study explored the classroom management practices of elementary school teachers in Bangladesh. The author found that teachers who used positive reinforcement, provided clear rules and expectations, and engaged students in classroom activities were more effective in managing classroom behavior.

Moreover, Sahoo and Das (2020) examined the classroom management techniques used by elementary school teachers in India. The authors found that effective strategies included setting clear rules and expectations, providing positive reinforcement, using proactive strategies to prevent misbehavior, and building positive relationships with students. They also found that teachers who were consistent in their approach and used a variety of techniques were more successful in managing classroom behavior.

Additionally, a study by Robertson and Murrell (2013) investigated the effects of consistent classroom management practices on elementary school students' behavior. The study found that teachers who consistently applied rules and consequences had better-managed classrooms and fewer behavior problems. More so, a study by Pekrun and Elliot (2009) investigated the effects of rewards on student motivation in elementary school classrooms. The study found that students who received rewards for good behavior were more motivated to engage in classroom activities and had better academic outcomes.

These studies provide evidence for the importance of maintaining discipline and morale in the classroom, and highlight effective strategies that teachers can use to promote positive behavior and create a positive learning environment.

Role of the Experiences that Shaped the Beliefs, Attitudes, and Commitment of Public Elementary School Teachers Pertaining to their Teaching Competence

In the discussion on the roles of the experiences that shaped the beliefs, attitudes, and commitment of public elementary school teachers pertaining to their teaching competence, some essential themes emerged from the responses of the participants. These themes include Teaching with a heart, Thoughtfulness in the pedagogy, and Steadfast in teaching.

Teaching with a Heart. This is the resulting theme that emerged upon analyzing the responses of the participants regarding the roles of experiences that shaped their beliefs towards teaching competence. This theme highlights the significance of bringing passion, empathy, and genuine care into the teaching practice. By integrating feelings in teaching, teachers aim to go beyond addressing students' intellectual aspects and prioritize the heart of the learners. Teachers are sensitive towards the students' diverse needs and experiences, creating a safe and inclusive environment that fosters positive relationships. By being responsive to the needs of the learners, teachers adapt instructional strategies to cater to different learning styles and provide personalized support.

Furthermore, they demonstrate awareness of the strengths and weaknesses of students, allowing them to tailor guidance and foster a growth mindset. Ultimately, the theme emphasizes the importance of creating a compassionate and inclusive learning environment that nurtures both the intellectual and emotional growth of students.

Further, the result of this study reinforces the study by Nel et al. (2014) which found that educators who cultivate deep connections and authentic relationships in their teaching practice contribute to a more engaging and supportive learning environment. Furthermore, the theme corroborates with the study of Thompson (2017) which highlighted the importance of bringing passion, empathy, and genuine care into the classroom, stressing the need to address not only students' intellectual aspects but also their emotional well-being. Additionally, Sutton and Wheatley (2003) discuss the impact of teachers' emotions on teaching and student outcomes, highlighting the role of teacher self-efficacy in fostering student achievement. More so, Woolfolk Hoy and Davis (2006) further emphasize the link between teacher self-efficacy and student success, highlighting the importance of educators' belief in their ability to positively influence student learning.

Furthermore, the finding is in consonance with what Pekrun and Elliot (2017) had found out that teachers who created emotionally supportive learning environments had a positive impact on student achievement and well-being. Further, a recent meta-analysis by Zhang et al. (2021) found that integrating emotions in teaching can have a positive impact on various student learning outcomes, including academic achievement, motivation, and social-emotional development. These studies suggest that teachers should not only focus on the cognitive development of their students but also consider the affective domain and the role of emotions in learning.

Moreover, Roorda et al. (2017) found that positive teacher-student relationships characterized by warmth, trust, and emotional support were associated with increased student engagement and achievement. Graziano et al. (2015) demonstrated the effectiveness of incorporating mindfulness practices into elementary instruction to promote self-regulation, emotional regulation, and social-emotional learning among students.

Additionally, Osher et al. (2016) emphasized the need for positive school climates that prioritize social-emotional learning, promote positive behavior, and foster a sense of belonging among students. A study by Brackett et al. (2021) highlighted the effectiveness of social-emotional learning programs in elementary schools, which aim to promote skills such as self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making. Finally, Jennings et al. (2017) found that teachers who were trained in mindfulness practices were better equipped to regulate their own emotions, which had positive effects on their classroom climate and student outcomes.

Thoughtfulness in Pedagogy. This is the resulting theme that emerged upon analyzing the responses of the participants as regards the role of experiences that shaped their attitudes towards teaching competence. Participants emphasized the importance of flexibility and versatility in planning and teaching. They highlighted that these qualities are essential components of a teacher's pedagogical creativity, allowing them to design effective classroom activities that engage students and facilitate their learning. The participants acknowledged the need for teachers to be adaptable and creative in their approach to teaching, as each student has unique learning needs and styles. They stressed that the ability to adjust their teaching methods to accommodate these differences is crucial for successful instruction and positive student outcomes.

This result supports the findings of a study by Lee and Kim (2020) who found that teachers who were more adaptable and creative in their approach to instruction were better able to engage students and facilitate their learning. Similarly, a study by Wang and Turner (2016) found that teachers who were able to modify their teaching strategies to accommodate students' unique learning needs and styles had a positive impact on student outcomes. These findings support the study conducted by Yilmaz (2018), which found that teachers who were able to adjust their teaching methods to meet the needs of individual students were more successful in promoting academic achievement.

It was further reinforced by Li et al. (2021) who examined the relationship between teachers' instructional practices and students' academic achievement in Chinese primary schools. They found that teachers who employed more flexible and differentiated instructional practices had students who demonstrated higher academic achievement. In another study, Chen et al. (2020) explored the effects of teachers' instructional flexibility on students' creativity. They found that teachers who exhibited greater instructional flexibility in their teaching practices had students who showed higher levels of creativity. Furthermore, a study by Ogunniyi and Ogundipe (2017) investigated the impact of teachers' pedagogical flexibility on students' learning outcomes in Nigerian primary schools. They found that teachers who were more flexible in their approach to instruction had students who showed greater academic achievement and higher levels of engagement in the classroom.

Steadfast in Teaching. The essential theme that emerged from the responses of the participants about their commitment pertaining to their teaching competence is steadfast in teaching. The concept of being steadfast in teaching implies a resolute dedication and unwavering commitment to the profession. It suggests that effective teachers are persistent, reliable, and unwavering in their efforts to provide quality education and support to their students. By remaining steadfast, teachers demonstrate their strong commitment to continuous improvement, professional growth, and the success of their students.

Further, the importance of being steadfast in teaching as a theme has been consistently emphasized in various studies. The finding confirms the result of the study done by Lomas et al. (2019) which found that teachers who were passionate about their work were

more likely to engage in professional development activities and use innovative teaching methods in the classroom. In another study by Schaufeli et al. (2019), they found that teachers who had a strong sense of personal fulfillment and engagement in their work were less likely to experience burnout and more likely to have positive attitudes towards their profession.

Furthermore, Hattie's meta-analysis (2003) revealed the significance of teacher qualities such as motivation, commitment, and effectiveness in influencing student outcomes. Similarly, Kunter et al. (2013) highlighted the relationship between teacher professional competence and instructional quality, emphasizing the importance of effective teaching practices.

Moreover, Day and Gu's book (2010) discussed the changing nature of teaching and the need for motivation and resilience in the face of challenges. Adding on, Woolfolk Hoy and Davis (2006) examined the influence of teacher self-efficacy on student achievement, underscoring the importance of teachers' belief in their ability to positively impact student learning. Giallo et al. (2017) explored the link between teacher self-efficacy and inclusive teaching practices, emphasizing the role of teachers' confidence in meeting diverse student needs.

Finally, a study by Hargreaves and Fullan (2019) emphasized the importance of teachers having a sense of purpose and passion in their work, as it can lead to increased job satisfaction, improved teaching practices, and ultimately, better student outcomes.

Data Integration on the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

In this section, the researcher applied the merging of relevant quantitative and qualitative findings on the status of metacognitive awareness, work task motivation, and the status of teaching competence among public elementary school teachers in Region XI. The two sets of data were compared for their similarities and their differences. The function of merging analysis is to let the quantitative and qualitative data either support or oppose each other.

Metacognitive Awareness. On this focal point under the category of Planning which has an item specifically regarding organizing their time to best accomplish their teaching goals scored very high and when merged to qualitative results, converged with the essential Theme Appropriateness of learning- task designs.

These are several studies that can support the results obtained in the analysis. The results confirm the study conducted by Schraw et al. (2006) which examined the role of metacognitive awareness, particularly in the category of planning, in science education. Their research underscored that effective time management and the organization of time to accomplish teaching goals are crucial elements of self-regulated learning. Such skills were found to enhance the design of appropriate learning tasks. Similarly, Zimmerman (2002) provided an overview of self-regulated learning, highlighting the significance of metacognitive processes, including planning, for academic achievement. Zimmerman emphasized that effective planning, such as organizing time efficiently, plays a critical role in self-regulated learning, contributing to the successful appropriateness of learning-task designs.

Moreover, Pintrich and De Groot (2003) conducted research on student self-regulation and found that effective planning and time management strategies positively influenced academic achievement. Similarly, Azevedo and Cromley (2004) investigated the relationship between metacognition, strategy use, and learning outcomes, and their findings demonstrated that effective planning, including time organization, was associated with improved learning performance.

For the same category of Planning, specifically on the item about setting their specific teaching goals before they start teaching scored very high. The findings of the data integration surfaced in the qualitative results, which are attributed to the essential theme leading to the Appropriateness of learning- task designs.

The qualitative data supported the notion that effective goal-setting in teaching contributes to the development of well-designed learning tasks that are suitable for the learners' needs and enhance the overall learning experience.

Several studies conducted after 2000 provide support for the relationship between effective goal-setting in teaching, the development of well-designed learning tasks, and the enhancement of the overall learning experience. This idea is consistent with the study by Bandura (2001) which emphasizes the role of goal-setting in self-regulated learning, highlighting how setting specific goals can enhance motivation and achievement. Additionally, Locke and Latham (2002) present a comprehensive theory of goal-setting and task motivation, emphasizing the positive impact of setting specific, challenging goals on performance. In addition, Pintrich and Schunk's book (2002) explores the role of goal-setting in motivating learners and designing meaningful learning tasks.

Moreover, Harackiewicz et al. (2000) highlight the importance of aligning goals with tasks, showing how effective goal-setting practices can influence interest and performance outcomes over time.

These studies collectively support the notion that effective goal-setting in teaching contributes to the development of well-designed learning tasks that are suitable for learners' needs, leading to an enhanced overall learning experience.

For the category, Procedural Knowledge item having a specific reason for choosing each teaching technique they use in class, scored very high. Additionally, the item being aware of what teaching techniques they use while they are teaching scored very high. Further, item using helpful teaching techniques automatically also scored very high. When merged with the qualitative results, it was found to be converging with the essential theme Appropriateness of learning-task designs.

The study by van Merriënboer et al. (2002) emphasized the importance of selecting appropriate teaching methods based on the learning objectives. The authors argued that effective instructional design involves identifying the learning objectives first and then choosing the appropriate teaching methods to achieve those objectives. This means that teachers need to possess procedural knowledge, which includes the ability to select and use various teaching techniques based on their knowledge of the content, students' needs, and the learning objectives.

Similarly, the study by Mayer and Moreno (2003) found that the use of appropriate teaching techniques can enhance student learning and engagement. The authors argued that when teachers use techniques such as multimedia presentations and interactive activities, students are more likely to be actively engaged in the learning process. These findings highlight the importance of teachers being aware of the techniques they are using during instruction and being able to select appropriate techniques that match the learning objectives and the needs of their students. Overall, the results of the study on procedural knowledge suggest that teachers need to possess a strong understanding of various teaching techniques and be able to use them effectively to promote student learning and engagement. This requires teachers to continuously develop their procedural knowledge and to reflect on the effectiveness of the techniques they are using in the classroom.

Another study supported by the findings in the Procedural Knowledge category is the work of Rosenshine (2012). In his research, Rosenshine identified a set of teaching principles that promote effective instruction. One of these principles is the use of explicit instruction, which involves breaking down complex skills into smaller, more manageable components and providing clear explanations and demonstrations. Rosenshine's work underscores the importance of teachers possessing a wide range of teaching techniques and strategies to effectively convey information to students. Moreover, it highlights the importance of teachers being intentional in their selection and use of teaching techniques, which aligns with the results of the present study. For the category, Declarative Knowledge items being aware of the strengths and weaknesses in their teaching, knowing what skills are most important in order to be a good teacher, having control over how well they teach, and knowing what they are expected to teach scored very high. When merged with the qualitative results, it was found to be converging with the essential theme Mindfulness of teaching-learning strategies.

This idea is supported by a study conducted by Richardson and Placier (2001), which found that effective teachers possess both content knowledge and pedagogical knowledge, including an understanding of their own teaching strengths and weaknesses. Similarly, a study by Darling-Hammond and Bransford (2005) highlighted the importance of teachers having a deep understanding of the subject matter they teach, as well as the ability to adapt instruction to meet the diverse needs of their students. These findings underscore the importance of teachers possessing declarative knowledge and continually reflecting on their teaching practice to improve their effectiveness.

In addition, a study by Slegers et al. (2008) provides further support for the importance of teachers' declarative knowledge. The study found that teachers' pedagogical content knowledge, which includes knowledge of the subject matter and how to teach it effectively, was positively associated with student achievement. This suggests that teachers who have a strong understanding of what they are expected to teach and how to teach it can have a significant impact on student learning outcomes.

Furthermore, the qualitative results of the study on declarative knowledge in teaching indicate that being aware of one's teaching strengths and weaknesses and having control over one's teaching can contribute to being a resourceful teacher and learning with an open mind. These findings underscore the importance of teachers possessing a strong foundation of declarative knowledge as a basis for effective teaching practice.

Work Task Motivation. This is another focal point that exhibits a converging nature when the quantitative and qualitative results were merged. For the category Intrinsic Motivation item, liking the tasks they are doing scored very high and directly converge with qualitative data with the essential Mindfulness of Teaching-Learning Strategies. It is evident that individuals who express a genuine enjoyment for their tasks are more likely to exhibit intrinsic motivation and possess an open mindset for learning experiences in order to continuously improve their teaching.

This study is in congruence with the study by Reeve and Tseng (2011) which found that intrinsic motivation, or the enjoyment of the task itself, is a crucial factor in enhancing teacher performance. The study also found that teachers who have high levels of intrinsic motivation tend to be more innovative and proactive in seeking out professional development opportunities. Similarly, a study by Li et al. (2019) demonstrated that teacher intrinsic motivation is positively associated with teacher engagement and well-being.

To further support these results, additional studies have examined the relationship between intrinsic motivation and task enjoyment. For instance, Ryan and Deci (2000) emphasized the importance of intrinsic motivation in promoting optimal functioning and self-determined behavior. Their research highlighted that individuals who have a genuine interest and enjoyment in the tasks they are engaged in are more likely to be intrinsically motivated. Similarly, Harackiewicz et al. (2002) explored the concept of intrinsic motivation in the academic context, demonstrating that task enjoyment and interest play a crucial role in fostering intrinsic motivation and enhancing learning outcomes. These studies reinforce the notion that individuals who find joy and satisfaction in the tasks they are performing are more likely to be intrinsically motivated and open to learning experiences.

Another study by Darling-Hammond and Richardson (2009) found that effective teaching involves the ability to make ongoing adjustments in response to student needs. The study emphasizes the importance of teachers being flexible and responsive to the diverse

needs of their students and continually seeking to improve their instructional practices.

Teaching Competence. On this focal point, the quantitative results corroborate with the qualitative findings. The items under the category of Presentation Skills reflected a very high average. In this category, participants scored very high on items that reflect their nature in capturing the attention of the learners and holding by a variety of cues, including postures, motions, gestures, changing speech patterns, focusing, changing interaction styles, pausing, and oral-visual switching and using deliberate silence and nonverbal cues to increase learners' participation. When this quantitative finding is merged with teaching competence, a converging of data is formed with the essential theme Established teacher presence.

Moreover, the finding supports several studies that disclosed that effective presentation skills and teacher presence are important components of teaching competence. First, the result confirms what Johnson and Focht (2009) found in their study that teacher presence, established through effective video introductions, creates a sense of community and improves student engagement in online courses. Furthermore, the finding of the study conforms with what Prain and Hand (2015) revealed, which highlighted the importance of teachers' personal practical knowledge of teaching nature of science, which includes the use of effective presentation skills and the establishment of teacher presence, in promoting student learning.

In addition, Ross (2008) found that self-assessment of teacher presentation skills is a reliable and valid measure of teaching competence. Moreover, Sahlberg (2011) emphasized the role of effective teacher presence and presentation skills in the Finnish educational system, which is consistently ranked among the highest-performing in the world. These studies collectively suggest that effective presentation skills and teacher presence play a significant role in promoting student engagement and learning, and are important components of teaching competence.

For the same category of presentation skills, specifically on the item about initiating learners' participation in the classroom by responding to their teacher, giving their idea and reacting to others' ideas scored very high. This quantitative data converged with the qualitative data in which the participants mentioned that the teacher's presence promotes student engagement and results to an essential theme Established teacher presence.

The results indicate that initiating learners' participation, as well as the teacher's presence, are important factors in promoting student engagement. This suggests that when students feel acknowledged and supported by their teacher, they are more likely to engage actively in the learning process, leading to increased student engagement and participation.

Several studies have explored the impact of initiating learners' participation in the classroom and the significance of teacher presence on student engagement. Particularly, Hmelo-Silver et al. (2007) examined the role of teacher scaffolding in promoting engagement and achievement in problem-based and inquiry learning. Additionally, Eddy and Hogan (2014) investigated the effects of increased course structure, including teacher-initiated activities and opportunities for student participation, on engagement and learning outcomes. Fredricks et al. (2004) conducted a comprehensive review that highlighted the importance of student participation and teacher presence in school engagement. Further, Van Laer et al. (2017) explored students' perceptions of blended learning environments, including aspects related to teacher presence and student participation, and their relationship with learning outcomes

Moreover, for the same category, the presentation skills item giving clear, interrelated, and meaningful statements that created sets and generated conclusions, had relevance, continuity, proper vocabulary, fluency, and no vague words helped explain concepts and principles was scored very high. When merged with the qualitative results, it was found to be converging with the essential theme of Higher-level thinking skills reinforcement.

More so, this suggests that the ability to effectively communicate ideas and concepts using clear, meaningful, and well-structured statements is closely linked to reinforcing higher-level thinking skills among learners. By presenting information in a coherent and interconnected manner, using appropriate vocabulary, and avoiding vagueness, teachers can facilitate a deeper understanding and engagement with complex concepts and principles.

Adding on, the results of the mentioned studies provide strong support for the findings that effective presentation skills, such as giving clear, interrelated, and meaningful statements, play a crucial role in reinforcing higher-level thinking skills among students. Also, Wilson and Wilson (2007) conducted a study exploring the benefits of online resources, social networking, and digital libraries in enhancing learning outcomes. They found that these tools can provide students with access to a wealth of information, facilitate collaboration and knowledge sharing, and promote higher-level thinking skills through interactive and engaging learning experiences. Similarly, Garr (2009) emphasized the importance of effective presentation design and delivery. The study delved into techniques for creating visually appealing and impactful presentations that capture the audience's attention, enhance understanding, and support higher-level thinking.

Additionally, Mayer and Moreno (2003) investigated strategies to reduce cognitive load in multimedia learning. Their research revealed that by presenting information in a well-structured and visually organized manner, learners can better focus their cognitive resources, leading to improved higher-level thinking and learning outcomes. Furthermore, Dwyer et al. (2004) examined the role of teacher beliefs and practices in fostering student engagement and achievement in online classrooms. They found that effective presentation skills, such as clear communication and well-structured presentations, can facilitate deeper understanding and promote higher-order thinking

among students.

Collectively, these studies provide compelling evidence for the positive impact of effective presentation skills on higher-level thinking, highlighting the importance of incorporating various instructional strategies and creating engaging learning environments to enhance cognitive engagement and academic achievement.

Further, for the same category of presentation skills, items 2 and 3, asking questions that were appropriate, well structured, properly put, adequate in number, and made learners participate, and providing probing questions that helped learners develop critical awareness by motivating them to seek out more information, refocus, redirect, and increase their critical awareness were scored very high and converged with qualitative results with essential theme Higher-level thinking skills reinforcement.

Furthermore, the essential theme of higher-level thinking skills reinforcement through effective questioning supports a recent study done by Brookhart (2021) The author emphasizes the importance of teachers asking higher-order questions that challenge students to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information. This aligns with the high scores of the presentation skills items related to asking appropriate, well-structured, and probing questions that encourage learners to develop critical awareness. Another study by Black and William (2018) emphasizes the importance of formative assessment, which includes questioning, as a means of promoting higher-level thinking skills. The authors suggest that formative assessment can help teachers identify gaps in students' understanding and provide timely feedback to support their learning.

Additionally, a study by Krathwohl (2019) highlights the importance of teachers using a variety of questioning techniques to support students' cognitive development, including open-ended questions, reflective questions, and questions that promote metacognition. These studies support the importance of effective questioning in promoting higher-level thinking skills, as found in the present study.

The next focal point of teaching competence is the item under the category of closing skills, the items summarizing the lesson's important points, past knowledge and current knowledge connected, providing chances for applying current knowledge presented, and knowledge connected to future learning, and giving an assignment to the learners which are appropriate, suited to individual differences, relevant to the content taught, and adequate were scored very high. When merged with the qualitative results, it was found to be converging with the essential theme of Higher-level thinking skills reinforcement.

The finding suggests that the closing skills used by teachers, such as summarizing important points, connecting past and current knowledge, providing opportunities for applying knowledge and assigning appropriate tasks, have a significant impact on reinforcing higher-level thinking skills among students. When teachers effectively utilize these skills to wrap up a lesson, they help students make connections between different concepts, apply their learning to practical situations, and foster deeper understanding.

This is in congruence with the study by Hattie and Timperley (2007) who conducted a comprehensive review of research on the power of feedback. They emphasized the importance of providing timely and specific feedback to students, highlighting areas of strength and areas for improvement. Consequently, their findings indicated that feedback has a significant impact on student learning and can promote higher-level thinking. Moreover, feedback encourages students to analyze, evaluate, and reflect on their work.

Similarly, the study corroborates with the study of Marzano (2012) which focused on closing the achievement gap through effective teaching strategies. He emphasized the importance of closing skills, such as summarizing important points and connecting past and current knowledge. In addition, the author highlighted the role of these skills in helping students make connections between concepts, synthesize information, and engage in critical thinking. As a result, by employing these closing skills, teachers can foster higher-level thinking and support students in reaching their full potential.

Additionally, Wiliam (2011) explored the concept of embedded formative assessment, which involves ongoing feedback and assessment practices. Wiliam emphasized that effective feedback and assessment should be used to guide instruction and promote higher-level thinking skills. Consequently, by providing students with timely feedback, teachers can identify gaps in understanding and provide targeted support to enhance critical thinking and problem-solving abilities.

Further, Darling-Hammond and Bransford (2005) discussed the preparation of teachers for a changing world. They highlighted the importance of equipping teachers with the skills and knowledge necessary to foster higher-level thinking among students. The authors emphasized the need for teachers to be adept at closing skills, such as summarizing key points and connecting knowledge to real-world applications. Ultimately, by incorporating these closing skills into their teaching practices, educators can support students in developing higher-order thinking skills and preparing them for success in an evolving society.

For the category managerial skills, the items acknowledging learners who are present as those who are absent, rewarding good attendance while discouraging bad attendance, and verifying good attendance with questions and nonverbal cues scored very high and when merged with qualitative results, converged with the essential theme Discipline and Morale Maintenance. The result suggests that within the category of managerial skills, specific items related to attendance management received high scores and were closely associated with the essential theme of maintaining discipline and morale. This implies that teachers who prioritize acknowledging and rewarding good attendance while addressing issues of absenteeism contribute to the overall discipline and positive atmosphere in the classroom.

The essential theme maintain discipline and morale through effective classroom management confirms numerous studies which have consistently highlighted the positive influence of consistent attendance on the overall classroom climate and student engagement (Rumberger, 2011). When teachers prioritize the acknowledgment and recognition of good attendance, students tend to develop a stronger sense of belonging and responsibility towards their education (Evertson & Weinstein, 2006). This connection between attendance and a positive classroom environment is crucial for fostering a conducive learning atmosphere.

Conversely, research has also demonstrated a link between high rates of absenteeism and discipline issues within classrooms (Gottfried, 2010). By addressing absenteeism and discouraging instances of bad attendance, teachers can establish clear expectations and create a disciplined learning environment (Marzano & Marzano, 2021). The consistent emphasis on attendance helps set a foundation of accountability and punctuality, which contributes to a focused and orderly classroom atmosphere.

Additionally, verifying attendance through the use of questions and nonverbal cues serves as a valuable tool for effective classroom management (Emmer & Stough, 2001). This practice not only ensures that students are actively engaged in the learning process but also reinforces the importance of regular attendance. By using such strategies, teachers can create an organized and well-structured learning environment, promoting student participation and reducing disruptions.

Overall, these findings highlight the significant role of attendance management in shaping the classroom climate and supporting student achievement. By prioritizing good attendance, discouraging absenteeism, and implementing strategies to verify attendance, educators contribute to the development of a positive and disciplined learning environment that fosters student engagement and success.

The last focal point is the significant influence of metacognitive awareness and work task motivation toward teaching competence. In particular, metacognitive awareness and work task motivation toward teaching competence, specifically work task motivation had significantly influenced the teaching competence of public elementary school teachers. When this quantitative finding was merged with qualitative results, a converging nature in the roles of experiences that shaped the attitudes of public elementary school teachers about their teaching competence is highlighted by the essential theme: thoughtfulness in pedagogy.

The finding suggests that teachers who possess metacognitive awareness and exhibit strong work task motivation are more thoughtful and reflective in their pedagogical practices. They are likely to engage in continuous learning, self-reflection, and professional development to enhance their teaching skills. Further, this study underscores the significance of fostering metacognitive awareness and intrinsic motivation among teachers to improve their teaching competence and promote effective pedagogy in public elementary schools.

Supporting these results, Schunk and Zimmerman (2008) emphasize the crucial role of intrinsic motivation and self-awareness in enhancing academic performance and competence. Their research underscores the significance of metacognitive strategies and motivation in promoting effective teaching practices. Additionally, Pintrich (2004) presents a conceptual framework that highlights the importance of metacognition in fostering effective learning strategies and academic success.

Furthermore, Artino and Stephens (2009) examine the relationship between academic motivation, self-regulation, and learning outcomes in online education settings. Their study emphasizes the importance of intrinsic motivation and self-awareness in promoting effective learning, which directly relates to teaching competence. Additionally, Schraw et al. (2006) investigate the role of metacognition in science education and stress the significance of metacognitive strategies in enhancing students' understanding and problem-solving skills. These studies provide theoretical and empirical support for the influence of metacognitive awareness and work task motivation on teaching competence, aligning with the findings of the present study.

Moreover, another focal point is the significant influence of the metacognitive awareness and work task motivation towards teaching competence specifically task motivation. When this quantitative finding was merged with qualitative results, a converging nature in the roles of experiences that shaped the commitment of public elementary school teachers about their teaching competence is highlighted by the essential theme: Steadfast in teaching. This underscores the importance of unwavering dedication and perseverance in the teaching profession. In essence, the result emphasizes that cultivating metacognitive awareness and fostering strong work task motivation are crucial factors in developing and maintaining a high level of competence among elementary school teachers.

This finding is consistent with the work of previous studies such as that by research has consistently emphasized the crucial role of dedication and perseverance in the context of elementary school teaching. Boyd et al. (2009) conducted an extensive analysis examining the relationship between teacher preparation and student achievement. Their findings revealed that teachers who exhibited steadfastness in their profession, coupled with effective preparation, had a positive impact on student outcomes. This highlights the importance of teachers' unwavering commitment to their students' success. This finding concurred with the work conducted by Johnson and Birkeland (2003) which explored the career decisions of new teachers and found that a strong sense of success and a commitment to making a difference motivated them to remain in the profession. In another study, Ingersoll and Strong (2011) examined the impact of induction and mentoring programs for beginning teachers. They discovered that teachers who received support and guidance in their early years were more likely to persist in their careers and demonstrate resilience in the face of challenges. Collectively, these studies highlight the significance of dedication and perseverance in elementary school teaching. They emphasize the positive effects of teachers' unwavering commitment to student outcomes and the importance of resilience in overcoming challenges. By remaining steadfast in their profession, elementary school teachers can create a supportive and engaging learning environment that fosters student success.

Implication for Educational Practice

In the field of education, there has been a growing interest in exploring the relationship between metacognitive awareness, work task motivation, and teaching competence among public elementary school teachers. Recent research has shown that teachers who possess high levels of metacognitive awareness and work task motivation tend to be more effective in promoting student learning outcomes. The outcomes of this scholarly investigation yielded substantial implications for the realm of educational practice, particularly in shaping the decisions and actions of educational leaders within the Department of Education (DepEd).

The gathered data from this research serve as a valuable resource that can inform and guide DepEd leaders in effectively allocating their attention and resources to address the multifaceted issues faced by teachers. Specifically, the comprehensive understanding of teachers' work task motivation derived from this study provides invaluable insights that can facilitate the identification of specific areas where additional support and interventions are urgently required to enhance teacher motivation, satisfaction, and overall well-being.

Furthermore, the discernment obtained from examining teaching competence provides practical guidance and strategic direction for DepEd teachers to actively engage in reflective practice, seek meaningful feedback from their colleagues and supervisors, and continually refine their instructional approaches. By fostering a culture of ongoing professional growth and creating an environment conducive to collaboration and knowledge sharing, DepEd can effectively empower teachers to constantly enhance their pedagogical skills and maintain a consistently high level of teaching competence. This approach enables teachers to adapt their instructional strategies to cater to the diverse needs of their students and ensure optimal educational outcomes.

Moreover, the profound insights derived from investigating metacognitive awareness underscore the critical importance of teachers' mindfulness of their cognitive processes, thinking strategies, and metacognitive skills in upholding teaching competence. This finding emphasizes the profound dedication and commitment of teachers to their noble profession, their unwavering adherence to the ethical standards of the education field, and their profound sense of responsibility towards their students and the wider community they serve.

By cultivating and promoting metacognitive awareness and work task motivation among DepEd teachers, the educational system can nurture a vibrant and dynamic learning environment that facilitates the continuous improvement and professional growth of educators, leading to the delivery of high-quality education and holistic student development. By incorporating these findings into educational policies and practices, DepEd can effectively support and empower teachers, optimize student learning outcomes, and cultivate a culture of excellence and lifelong learning within the educational system.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn from the findings of the study:

The status of metacognitive awareness was rated very high. This implies that the teachers' metacognitive awareness was evident and always manifested as they effectively carry out their responsibilities in the DepEd. This indicates that teachers have a strong awareness of their cognitive abilities and can effectively manage their thinking and learning strategies. Hence, the public elementary school teachers in Region XI are considered effective and possess the said metacognitive awareness.

The status of work task motivation was rated high. This result implies that the teachers' work task motivation was always demonstrated in Region XI. They are likely to exhibit enthusiasm, dedication, and a proactive approach to fulfilling their work-related responsibilities. Further, the status of teaching competence was very high which means that teaching competence of public elementary school teachers was always evident. This implies that they consistently demonstrated proficiency in instructional strategies, subject matter knowledge, classroom management, and other essential aspects of effective teaching. Their high rating in teaching competence indicates that they are capable and skilled educators who consistently deliver quality education to their students.

With regard to the individual influence of the data gathered the results showed that the metacognitive awareness of teachers and teaching competence had no significant influence. The results revealed that for every unit increase in the status of metacognitive awareness of public elementary school teachers, there is a corresponding decrease in their teaching competence. Meanwhile, the same cannot be said for the work task motivation and the teaching competence of public elementary school teachers.

These results implied that the work task motivation of public elementary school teachers plays a significant role in their teaching competence. Further with the combined effect of metacognitive awareness and work task motivation as predictors of teaching competence, the results revealed that metacognitive awareness and work task motivation had significantly influenced the teaching competence of public elementary school teachers. This means that the metacognitive awareness combined with the manifestation of the work task motivation of public elementary school teachers, the level of teaching competence of teachers was being influenced.

Further, several essential themes emerged from the lived experiences of the participants. These themes are: design appropriate learning tasks, learn with an open mind, establish teacher presence, reinforce higher level thinking skills, and maintain discipline and morale. Further, the lived experiences of the participants shaped their beliefs, attitudes, and commitment toward teaching competence. For the participants, they believed that incorporating metacognitive strategies in teaching may lead to increased motivation and better teaching competence.

Furthermore, work task motivation, metacognitive awareness, and teaching competence are all important factors that can have a significant impact on individual and organizational outcomes. Motivated teachers tend to be more engaged, productive, and committed to their work, which can be influenced by job design, feedback, recognition, and growth opportunities. On the other hand, individuals with high levels of metacognitive awareness are better able to plan, set goals, reflect on their learning, and adjust their strategies as needed, leading to improved learning outcomes and more effective teaching practices. Teaching competence encompasses a range of skills, such as subject matter knowledge, lesson planning, and student assessment, and teachers who possess these skills have a positive impact on student learning. Therefore, promoting work task motivation, metacognitive awareness, and teaching competence can lead to better performance, greater satisfaction, and positive outcomes for all involved in both the workplace and educational settings.

Moreover, the study's findings suggest that teachers' beliefs, attitudes, and commitment towards their teaching competence are vital in shaping their motivation and metacognitive awareness. The study's results further emphasize the importance of setting personal goals and dedication in maintaining high levels of motivation and metacognitive awareness toward teaching competence. These findings have important implications for teacher training programs and professional development initiatives, which can focus on developing strategies to promote work task motivation and metacognitive awareness, as well as fostering teachers' beliefs, attitudes, and commitment toward their teaching competence.

Lastly, the quantitative findings corroborated with the qualitative results which means that the results in the qualitative phase are in consonance with the quantitative phase.

The following recommendations are presented based on the findings of the study:

Since the status of metacognitive awareness was very high, it can be maintained if public elementary school teachers continue to prioritize and cultivate their metacognitive skills and strategies. School leaders may provide professional development opportunities to support teachers in enhancing their teaching competence and aligning their skills with the needs of 21st-century students. Workshops, training sessions, and mentoring programs can be organized to help teachers acquire new knowledge, skills, and teaching strategies that are effective and evidence-based. Teachers can also be encouraged to participate in collaborative learning and peer support groups to share ideas and experiences with their colleagues.

Considering that the work task motivation of public elementary school teachers was very high and always demonstrated, teachers may continue to strive for excellence by setting specific and challenging goals, fostering a growth mindset, and seeking ongoing professional development opportunities to enhance their skills and knowledge. Furthermore, educational institutions may provide support to teachers by recognizing their achievements, creating a positive and supportive work environment, and implementing programs that promote teacher well-being and job satisfaction. Ultimately, by cultivating a culture of continuous improvement and investing in the professional development and well-being of teachers, school leaders may help to ensure that the public elementary school teachers are well-equipped to meet the diverse needs of their students and to prepare them for success in the future.

On the account of the status of teaching competence among public elementary school teachers was very high, this can be sustained if school administrators provide a supportive environment that encourages and recognizes the efforts of public elementary school teachers in maintaining their competence. The practice of giving awards and tokens of appreciation to outstanding teachers may be sustained or even be improved to make the practice more motivating. By taking these steps, public elementary school teachers can further enhance their teaching competence and continue to provide quality education to their students.

Since the metacognitive awareness and work task motivation were significant predictors of the teaching competence of public elementary school teachers, it can be sustained if educational institutions prioritize the development and enhancement of metacognitive awareness and work task motivation among their teaching staff. Training programs and workshops may be designed and implemented to help teachers improve their metacognitive abilities, such as planning, monitoring, and evaluating their teaching practices. Additionally, schools may create a conducive work environment that promotes work task motivation by providing support and incentives to teachers.

Future research can explore other factors that may influence teaching competence, such as emotional intelligence and cultural competence among others. It would also be interesting to investigate the effects of various interventions, such as coaching and mentoring, on the development of metacognitive awareness and work task motivation among teachers. Additionally, future studies may continue to benefit from using a mixed-methods approach to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the complex interplay of other variables other than those covered in the study. Moreover, it may be useful for future researchers to explore the generalizability of these findings to other contexts beyond public elementary schools, such as private schools or different levels of education.

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